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NI4OS-Europe

National Initiatives for Open Science in Europe

Deliverable D7.4

1st Dissemination and marketing report

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Abstract: Deliverable D7.4 – “1st Dissemination and marketing report” – provides an overview of the dissemination, communication and marketing activities, as well as project innovations and sustainability results during the first 18 months of the project.

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List of Acronyms

CoE	Centre of Excellence
EC	European Commission
e-IRG	e-Infrastructure Reflection Group
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IT	Information Technologies
LCT	License Clearance Tool
NOAD	National Open Access Desk
NOSCI	National Open Science Cloud Initiatives
OS	Open Science
OSC	Open Science Cloud
RDA	Research Data Alliance
R&D	Research and Development
R&E	Research and Education
RDM	Research Data Management
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
SMEs	Small and Medium Enterprises
TNC	Transnational Cooperation

Executive summary

What is the focus of this Deliverable?

Deliverable D7.4 “1st Dissemination and marketing report” represents the first report of the NI4OS-Europe dissemination and marketing activities. The focus of this deliverable is to provide a detailed overview of the dissemination and marketing results during the first 18 months of the NI4OS-Europe project. D7.4 also presents innovation activities, results, and update on the sustainability. D7.4 shows statistics about the dissemination events that are organized by the NI4OS-Europe project, as well as the ones with NI4OS-Europe presence. It gives an overview about the dissemination and use materials, web presence, social media and dissemination and training tools and documents.

What is next in the process to deliver the NI4OS-Europe results?

The deliverable and workflow progress are described in the project Annex-I – Description of the Action [1] and in the Project Amendment [1]. The conclusions and recommendations from this deliverable will help improve the future dissemination and marketing activities in all partner countries during the next project duration. It will further enhance the quality of the dissemination and marketing efforts. The initial dissemination and marketing plans defined in project deliverable D7.2 [3] were updated according to the project needs and COVID-19 pandemic, and we will continue to refine the plans. The dissemination materials, web pages and communication channels will continue to be regularly updated and kept active. The final report on the dissemination and marketing activities will be presented in D7.6 towards the end of the project.

What are the deliverable contents?

This deliverable starts with an introduction, presenting the general view of this deliverable, then 4 chapters present summary of activities and achievements of the 4 WP7 main tasks: dissemination, marketing, innovation and sustainability with their internal connection. The document ends with the conclusion. There are four Appendices presenting list of events, list of publications, list of presentations and list of marketing actions.

Conclusions and recommendations

The presented dissemination and marketing report for the first 18 months of the project is in-line with the initial dissemination and marketing plans presented in project deliverable D7.2 [3]. These plans were successfully updated according to the project needs in the COVID-19 situation, which did have an impact on project implementation. The planned events were held online, with a focus on social media and web presence, while some events were postponed for the coming period. The plans will be further updated depending on the situation.

1. Introduction

The deliverable D7.4 “1st Dissemination and marketing report” is the fourth deliverable in the framework of the NI4OS-Europe activity WP7 “Communication, marketing, sustainability and innovation”. This project activity has provided a platform for networking, collaboration and dissemination for the participants in the regional Open Science Cloud (OSC) ecosystem. D7.4 reports the WP7 work done and results achieved during the project period M01-M18. The work of the WP7 started from the first day of project lifetime and some of the accomplishments are already documented in the following deliverables: D7.1 “Internal and external communication platform” [2], D7.2 “Marketing, dissemination and sustainability plan” [3] and D7.3 “Promotional package” [4].

One year within this reporting period was spent in very unusual conditions – COVID-19 pandemic situation. The planned activities in the first deliverable D7.2 were affected – in the early 2020 some of the events and conferences were cancelled, and some postponed. The project reacted promptly in order to adapt to the COVID-19 situation, and proposed online schemes and a series of useful webinars and materials (e.g. “How to host a successful Virtual event?”), series of capacity building workshops in WP6, series of WP2 workshops, translation of important EOSC-related materials in local languages, etc., in order to help partners to organize successfully their local marketing and dissemination events in the new formats. Thus, the changes affected not only our work in communication and dissemination, but also the priorities and the very way the project works.

Deliverable D7.4 “1st Dissemination and marketing report” represents the report of NI4OS-Europe dissemination, marketing, innovation and sustainability activities during the first 18 months of the project. The document is organized as follows: after a short introduction, we present a summary of dissemination activities which includes overview of the dissemination and use material, the project web presence including project official web site [6], social media, project event portal [7], project training portal [10], wiki [12], calendar [9], and section NI4OS-Europe against COVID-19 [11]. Then a short description of main dissemination events (organized by the project, and project presentation at external events), and overview of media coverage, is presented. The next chapter 3 describes marketing activities complimentary to the dissemination activities, and reports on the implementation and results. Chapter 4 presents the implementation of the innovation strategy developed by the project and describes the results. Chapter 5 gives sustainability plan updates. The document ends with conclusions. The document is supported by four appendices containing the list of external events, the list of publications, the list of presentations and the list of marketing actions.

2. Dissemination activities' summary

2.1. Dissemination and use materials

2.1.1. Project materials

The project core promotional package is an essential tool for NI4OS-Europe marketing and communication activities. It is built on a common, consistent graphic style, establishing a strong brand. The core promotional material is comprised of the NI4OS-Europe Logo, brochure, presentation, roll ups and web banners.

NI4OS-Europe dissemination package is a major part of the overall project marketing and communication material and content that is constantly produced, such as announcements, newsletters, posters, power point presentations and social media posts, all significant elements for maximizing the effectiveness of the NI4OS-Europe expected outcomes.

The core promotional material is presented in detail in D.7.3 [4]. The project dissemination material is available on the NI4OS-Europe media corner [7].

2.1.1.1 Project logo

Figure 1: NI4OS-Europe logo and favicon

The logo is the basic element of NI4OS-Europe brand identity. All elements of the project material and infrastructure (brochure, presentation, posters and banners, website and social media accounts), have a common design approach in order to ensure consistent branding across all communication tools.

2.1.1.2 Project brochure

NI4OS-Europe corporate brochure provides in an intelligible and legible manner a meaningful overview of the project, its methodology and the benefits for its target communities. The printed brochure has been sent to the whole partnership in order to enhance dissemination via national channels.

Figure 2: NI4OS-Europe brochure

2.1.1.3 Project presentation

Figure 3: NI4OS-Europe presentation template

The project core presentation provides complete information about NI4OS-Europe, its structure and methodology, as well as the crucial work developed in each WP for the fulfilment of its objectives.

Additionally, a shorter version of the core presentation has been created to reflect the project methodology and outcomes. Special emphasis is given on the use of pictures, icons

and the project colors with the aim to highlight the information and messages that reflect the project value.

Figure 4: Front and back cover of NI4OS-Europe visual presentation

2.1.1.4 Project posters

NI4OS-Europe posters' use is meant to catch the attention of the project target groups and to establish the project brand during meetings, workshops and conferences, even when happening online, used as background banners. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic since the beginning of 2020, the use of the posters was limited in relation to the initial plan.

Figure 5: NI4OS-Europe posters

2.1.1.5 Roll-ups

The roll ups are and will be used for the events organized by NI4OS-Europe and/or events with NI4OS-Europe participation.

Figure 6: NI4OS-Europe roll ups

2.1.1.6 Web banners

The project web banners containing the main message “For Open Science Cloud”, are used in several ways to facilitate the marketing and communication activities: from social media posts to the NI4OS-Europe newsletters’ template, they create, enhance and maintain consistency in the project brand identity.

Figure 7: NI4OS-Europe web banners

2.1.1.7 Other material

Two additional brochures have been created as training material, providing insights and guidelines about the European Open Science Cloud and FAIR Data. The EOSC brochure describes the concept, the Governance Structure and the future of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), as well as the benefits for various stakeholders. The FAIR Data brochure provides guidelines on what FAIR Data is and how they can be managed so that they are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. The creation of the material is part of NI4OS-Europe training and user engagement activities addressing various stakeholders, in order to promote EOSC and FAIR principles and to facilitate the uptake of research data sharing across national research communities. It is available on the project training platform [9] and website [7], in all mother languages of the NI4OS-Europe area.

Figure 8: NI4OS-Europe brochures for EOSC and FAIR principles

Two informative posters describing NI4OS-Europe and its License Clearance tool were presented during the Open Science FAIR in Porto (16-18 Sept. 2019) and the RDA 16th Plenary Meeting, (9-12 November 2020), respectively.

The poster entitled “NI4OS-EUROPE: Building National Initiatives for Open Science in Europe” provides information on the objectives, the core actions, the expected outcomes and the target region of the project. The License Clearance tool poster briefly describes the features, workflow and benefits of the tool.

Figure 9: NI4OS-Europe posters

2.1.2. Project newsletter

Three newsletters have been released since NI4OS-Europe start. The newsletters reflect the plethora of initiatives and activities taking place, delivering significant results in the light of the project objectives.

The newsletters have been announced on the project social media accounts and they are also available on NI4OS-Europe and other websites:

- [NI4OS-Europe newsletter | Issue no.1 | April 2020](#)
- [NI4OS-Europe newsletter | Issue no.2 | July 2020](#)
- [NI4OS-Europe newsletter | Issue no.3 | November 2020](#)

Figure 10: NI4OS-Europe newsletters

2.2. NI4OS-Europe web presence

2.2.1. Official NI4OS-Europe web site

The official website of the project is accessible via <https://ni4os.eu>.

The website serves as a central source of information about the project structure, liaisons, activities and outcomes and it constitutes an essential tool for the project marketing and communication activities. It also provides access to NI4OS-Europe training platform, social media accounts and subscription option to the project news. The website is periodically assessed and restructured in order to reflect the project progress and to promote effectively its role and outcomes. NI4OS-Europe website is GDPR compliant.

The following picture presents the analytics of the website:

Figure 11: Statistics of site traffic

Country ?	Acquisition			Behavior		
	Users ? ↓	New Users ?	Sessions ?	Bounce Rate ?	Pages / Session ?	Avg. Session Duration ?
	3,159 % of Total: 73.88% (4,276)	3,182 % of Total: 74.05% (4,297)	7,258 % of Total: 86.53% (8,388)	56.70% Avg for View: 62.17% (-8.81%)	2.23 Avg for View: 2.07 (7.78%)	00:02:24 Avg for View: 00:02:05 (15.00%)
1. Greece	365 (11.50%)	365 (11.47%)	1,311 (18.06%)	45.69%	2.69	00:03:12
2. Serbia	163 (5.13%)	167 (5.25%)	532 (7.33%)	44.36%	2.58	00:02:30
3. Croatia	160 (5.04%)	161 (5.06%)	344 (4.74%)	55.52%	2.17	00:02:39
4. Hungary	159 (5.01%)	158 (4.97%)	673 (9.27%)	52.45%	2.65	00:03:00
5. Romania	144 (4.54%)	146 (4.59%)	361 (4.97%)	57.62%	2.16	00:02:14
6. Cyprus	141 (4.44%)	141 (4.43%)	398 (5.48%)	57.04%	1.98	00:02:07
7. Germany	132 (4.16%)	131 (4.12%)	177 (2.44%)	71.19%	1.77	00:01:10
8. Moldova	122 (3.84%)	122 (3.83%)	210 (2.89%)	51.90%	2.10	00:02:28
9. Slovenia	110 (3.46%)	110 (3.46%)	300 (4.13%)	47.33%	2.58	00:03:40
10. Bulgaria	107 (3.37%)	108 (3.39%)	502 (6.92%)	64.74%	1.86	00:02:28

Figure 12: The analytics of NI4OS-Europe web site (list of top ten)

2.2.2. NI4OS-Europe event portal

The project website is an essential tool for the project dissemination activities.

All the information about NI4OS-Europe meetings, technical workshops, training events, dissemination events and conferences is presented in the project calendar [8]. It is based on three thematic calendars (dissemination events & conferences, training workshops & webinars, and NI4OS-Europe related events), which are embedded in one, single page (<https://ni4os.eu/calendar>).

Figure 13: NI4OS-Europe calendar for all events

The Agenda tool [6] allows scheduling and organizing events, from simple meetings to complex workshops and conferences with sessions and contributions. It is based on CDS Indico software, which is free software, licensed under GNU General Public License (GPL) and is actively maintained. The NI4OS-Europe Agenda is provided as a category of the Indico installation hosted by GRNET. The following event categories have been set up in the Event Agenda tool:

- Meetings.
- Conferences | Dissemination events.
- Training workshops | Webinars.

All the national dissemination workshops are organized using the project Event Agenda tool [6]. The administrators help partners in posting all the necessary information: description of the event, registration of the participants, time table, uploading presentations and other materials useful for participants.

Figure 14: NI4OS-Europe event agenda tool

events.ni4os.eu/event/30/timetable/#20201120

National Dissemination event in Bulgaria

20 November 2020
Sofia
Europe/Sofia timezone

Overview
Timetable
Contribution List
My Conference
My Contributions
Registration
Participant List

Aneta Karaivanova, Todor Gurov
anet@parallel.bas.bg
gurov@parallel.bas.bg

Timetable

Fri 20/11

Print PDF Full screen Detailed view Filter

14:00	Welcome message and opening Sofia	Mrs Yanita Zherkova 14:00 - 14:05
	NI4OS-Europe Sofia	Prof. Aneta Karaivanova 14:05 - 14:25
	EOSC Sofia	Prof. Todor Gurov 14:25 - 14:45
	Bulgarian portal for Open Science Sofia	Mrs Hristiyaniya Ancheva 14:45 - 15:05
15:00	National Science program for ICT Sofia	Prof. Krassen Stefanov 15:05 - 15:25
	Bulgarian node of RDA Sofia	Prof. Ana Proykova 15:25 - 15:45
	National OS Initiative in Bulgaria and Bulgarian node of OpenAtr Sofia	Prof. Peter Stanchev 15:45 - 16:05
16:00	Q&A Sofia	16:05 - 16:25
	Conclusion & Wrap up Sofia	16:25 - 16:30

Figure 15: Example of an agenda for a NI4OS-Europe national dissemination event

2.2.3. NI4OS-Europe training portal

The NI4OS-Europe training portal available at <https://training.ni4os.eu/> is used as the main repository of training materials used and created by the project together with an integrated webinar system that is used to organize the virtual training events. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, all training events held so far have been held as webinars and thus the training portal webinar system has become one of the essential tools used for training. All recorded training webinars are available for future reference to all registered participants of the training, which is managed through the integration with the NI4OS-Europe event portal. To help support the project partners in the virtual organization of the training events, the training portal webinar system has been upgraded in June in order to support large webinars and to provide a richer set of interactive webinar features such as advanced polling, break out rooms, etc.

The training events have started early in the project, first with a group of train-the-trainers webinar series that were aiming to prepare the national training representatives, and then continued with the initial capacity building training events. Although the initial training plan had to be adjusted due to the pandemic, after a brief pause in the beginning the training activities are continuing according to the revised training plan, and currently the capacity building training events are almost completed, and the end-users training events are starting.

Figure 16: List of available courses in the NI4OS-Europe training portal

In January 2021, the training platform provides access to a total of 42 training courses to 475 registered users, see Figure 16. Nonetheless, the platform is also available to users without accounts, i.e. guest users. Each course has its own set of training materials. The courses are divided into 4 main categories: 9 train-the-trainers events, 14 capacity building events, 16 end-users trainings and 4 miscellaneous courses. Most of the train-the-trainer events have been organized in collaboration with other EOSC related projects such as EOSC-Hub and EGI, wherein experts have been invited to share their knowledge in topics such as FAIR data, data management plans, FitSM, etc. For the national capacity building and end-users trainings the national EOSC promoters and the OpenAIRE NOADS were also taking active part of the training activities. The NI4OS-Europe training portal is also used to host the EOSC and FAIR promotional materials and brochures translated into the partners native languages, see Figure 17. The current distribution of main topics and targeted audience of the training material available on the NI4OS-Europe training platform can be seen in Figure 18.

Figure 17: EOSC and FAIR brochures in the NI4OS-Europe training portal

Figure 18: NI4OS-Europe training portal dashboard view

Compared on the initial training plan, the training activities organized so far have exceeded the project KPIs. For an example, in addition to the original 5 train-the-trainer events, extra events have been organized such as one organized in collaboration with DANS and EOSC-Hub on the topic of domain specific protocols for data management plans, see Figure 16. Furthermore, a special training event on the topic of how to organize a virtual event has been developed to help partners redesign their training workshops and better adapt to the virtual webinar environments. Regarding the number of participants to the training events, the project KPI of 450 training events participants has been reached, not just by the number of registered users on the training platform, but also with the high number of training participants registered for each individual training event. For an example the train-the-trainers events were followed by over 50 participants on average, and most of the capacities building training events were held with over 30 participants on average. A detailed description of the training portal related activities will be provided in Deliverable D6.6: „Training report“.

2.2.4. NI4OS-Europe vs COVID-19

NI4OS-Europe vs COVID-19 initiative [10] provides the Fast Access Channel for available services, computational and other resources. We also want to share the information about COVID-19 and SARS-CoV-2 related projects and open data sets in the region and joint resources for Open Science such as public and community nomenclatures and guidelines.

NI4OS-Europe opened a fast track access channel to its services, tools and software for the scientific communities that perform extensive research to tackle the COVID-19. Computational resources have already been allocated to the Bioinformatics European Research Era Chair and the Bioinformatics Group at the Cyprus Institute of Neurology and Genetics. The research team has put their efforts in the multi-omics analysis and network-based integration towards a highly-informed decision regarding a short list of repurposed drugs and related to them natural products against COVID-19.

Some thematic services provided by the project for this problem are:

- ChemBioServer.
- FEPrepare.
- AFMM.
- Nanocrystal.

We collected the details and methods how partnering countries reacted on the COVID-19 crisis and tried to show the results on one unique page. Partners aggregated data on the topic, some made guidelines, some had information on medical support, education and society support and they shared with as many people as they could. There were national and regional initiatives. There were even some countries that made dashboards where they tracked all the new information on COVID-19, being updated frequently. These dashboards showed not only numbers and statistics but research results, publications, preprints and new methods. Some partners provided computational resources on COVID-19 research. Some made supporter applications for the scientific community and even for the wider public. We collected the various guidelines and protocols that came into action in the region.

2.2.5. **NI4OS-Europe wiki**

NI4OS-Europe Wiki [11] was created for finding information very quickly related to the project. It contains details on the Pre-production environment, On-boarded resources, candidates, resource providers. Important information can be found here on the tools that have been created by WP4, EOSC RoP Legal & Ethics Compliance, RePol Registry Policy Generator. The Wiki also gives access to the NI4OS-Europe policy documents and templates and COVID-19 resources. The database is being developed continuously.

Wiki is a great collaborative tool, which is to support communication and spreading information in a simple way. Wiki is to serve transparency for NI4OS-Europe.

Figure 19: NI4OS-Europe wiki page

situation totally changed because of COVID-19, and we had to change our plans and adapt our work to the new conditions. For example, we had plans for significant promotion of NI4OS-Europe during the Croatian presidency in the first half of 2020, but some of the events were cancelled, other held in different format. Next, our plan included 15 national dissemination events organized by the project in the first half of the project lifetime. Most of the partners expected that there would be an option to organize their events with physical presence but this did not happen. So, the project plan was updated in the summer 2020 and the events were organized online (using project training platform or other online platforms like Zoom). Summarized information about status of these events is given in Table 1 where the already performed events (8) are marked in green. Information about the national dissemination events can be found in the project web site [6] and their agenda is given in the project agenda system [7]. Short description of the national dissemination events is given in subsection 2.3.1. The other 7 national dissemination events are scheduled in the period March – May 2021.

The information about major events where NI4OS-Europe has been presented can also be found at the project web site [5]. The current number of these events is 8. Short descriptions are given in subsection 2.3.2. Additionally to this, each partner distributes project promotional materials at the main local project related events – reports of these activities can be found at the project 3-monthly reports. At the end of this section we give short summary.

№	Project Month	Organizer	Country	Framework [national/ regional]	Updated Project Month	Remarks
1	M03	13-UMUKM/12-Arnes	SI	National/collocated	M03, 14-15.11.2019	DONE
2	M06	19-UOM	ME	National	M06, 18.02.2020	DONE
3	M08	18-UKIM	MK	National	M15, 6.11.2020	DONE
4	M10	05-IICT	BG	National	M15, 20.11.2020	DONE
5	M12	21-IIAP	AM	National	M13, 28.09.2020	DONE
6	M14	11-UEFISCDI/10-ICI	RO	National	M14, 27.10.2020	DONE
7	M15	15-RCUB-UOB/14-IPB	RS	National	M16, 29.12.2020 M18, 24.02.2021	DONE
8	M09	17-UniBL	BA	National	M19, 02.03.2021	In progress
9	M06	01-GRNET/02-ATHENA	EL	National	M20	Postponed due to COVID-19

10	M08	06-SRCE	HR	National / collocated	M21	Postponed due to COVID-19
11	M14	04-UCY	CY	National	M20	Postponed due to COVID-19
12	M14	20-RENAM	MD	National	M20	Postponed due to COVID-19
13	M14	22-GRENA	GE	National	M19	Postponed due to COVID-19
14	M16	08-NIIFI- KIFU	HU	National	M23	Postponed due to COVID-19
15	M18	16-RASH	AL	National	M21	Postponed due to COVID-19

Table 1: NI4OS-Europe national dissemination events organized

The project organized a lot of online internal meetings and workshops presenting the WPs achievements and capacity building trainings to keep project team informed of current project achievements. The webinar “How to host a successful virtual event?” on 31 August 2020, organized by the WP7 team, was very helpful to partners. Also, materials related to EOSC and FAIR were translated to all local languages, and this helped a lot of partners in the organization of local events.

2.3.1. Details of NI4OS-Europe organized dissemination events

2.3.1.1 NI4OS-Europe national dissemination events

NI4OS-Europe national dissemination event in Bulgaria, November 20, 2020

<https://events.ni4os.eu/event/30/>

Because of COVID-19 pandemic the NI4OS-Europe national dissemination event in Bulgaria was held online on the 20th of November 2020. The event started with a presentation of the NI4OS-Europe project including the project results achieved during the first project year and the project plans for the next period, followed by a presentation of EOSC and its current status with an accent on the NI4OS-Europe contribution to EOSC. Then the main results in 2020 of other Bulgarian Open Science projects and initiatives were presented: Bulgarian Open Science Portal (www.bpos.bg), Open Science activities in the National Scientific Program on ICT, activities of the Bulgarian node of RDA (www.rda.bg) and of the Bulgarian node of OpenAir. Mrs. Yanita Zherkova, a chief officer in the Directorate “Science” in the Ministry of Education and Science presented the policy, documents and future actions in the area of Open Science.

Figure 21: Part of participants in the NI4OS-Europe national dissemination event in Bulgaria

62 participants attended the event representing: (i) policy-making and funding organizations (14.5%), (ii) research institutes (35.5%), universities (30.5%) and business organisations (6.5%), (iii) data and service providers including infrastructures and libraries (12.9%). The event ended with a discussion about future activities.

NI4OS-Europe national dissemination event in Romania, October 27, 2020

<https://events.ni4os.eu/event/28/>

On October 27, 2020, took place the first dissemination event organized by the Romanian partners in the NI4OS-Europe project: the Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding (UEFISCDI) and the National Institute for R&D in Informatics (ICI). Because of the COVID 19 pandemic, the event was delivered in a webinar format, with the full support of the WP7 representative in using the NI4OS-Europe event platform for promoting and registration activities.

The event was dedicated to all categories of the Open Science Cloud stakeholders in Romania, according to the project action plan towards building the National OSC Initiative. Representatives of research institutes and universities, e-Infrastructure and specific service providers, libraries, publishers and other interested parties were invited to attend the event.

The objective of the event was to inform participants about the overall project objectives and the results of the landscape survey run by the project about the Open Science awareness, the existing initiatives, infrastructures, services, policies, and stakeholders in this field. Also an overview of the Open Science/Open Data concepts and the activity of the Romanian OS Knowledge Hub (OSKH RO - UEFISCDI) were provided. In this context, a specific focus was put on research data management plan in the European and national context. The next major topic was the European Open Science Cloud ecosystem and the main NI4OS-Europe priorities in supporting the development of EOSC compliant infrastructure and services in the South-Est Europe. The final presentation was devoted to the FAIR principles due to their relevance in achieving higher transparency and reusability of research data. The timetable of the event is available at <https://events.ni4os.eu/event/28/timetable/#20201027> .

The event was attended by 41 participants representing policy-making and funding organizations (19%), research institutes (40%), universities (27%) and academic libraries (14%). The event aroused interest from participants who were constantly involved in discussions by formulating opinions, asking clarifications and expressing their intentions to follow the project developments.

NI4OS-Europe national dissemination event in Slovenia, November 14-15, 2019 collocated with the Conference “Open Research Data in Slovenia”

<https://events.ni4os.eu/event/12/>

The University of Maribor Library and ARNES organized the first Slovenian NI4OS-Europe national event called “Open Science 2019: Open research data in Slovenia and workshops for researchers” in cooperation with RDA Node Slovenia, the Young Academy of Slovenia society and the Ministry of Education, Science and Sports of the Republic of Slovenia during the national »Science Month«. The conference and workshops were held at the University of Maribor Library from the 14th to 15th November 2019. Almost 80 attendees from the Slovenian scientific community signed up for the event, including policymakers, service providers, librarians, researchers and students.

The conference enabled the exchange of information on the activities and plans of individual research data-related services and projects, an overview of the implementation of the principles of the National Strategy for Open Access to Research Data, and an overview of the current situation in individual areas within the Slovenian research community.

A special section of the programme was dedicated to NI4OS-Europe, called “National Initiative for Open Science in Slovenia”, which presented the NI4OS-Europe project and its methodology, as well as its plans in regards to FAIR principles implementation, the establishment of a national Open Science Cloud and the NI4OS-Europe landscape survey. Around 80 attendees from the Slovenian scientific community signed up for the event.

The workshops for researchers included face-to-face training by local and international trainers in open science, FAIR principles, research data management, open hardware, open peer review and open access publishing.

NI4OS-Europe national dissemination event in Serbia, December 29, 2020, collocated with the Open Science Pioneers Annual Meeting

<https://events.ni4os.eu/event/37/>

The first dissemination event in Serbia was organized as part of the third Annual Meeting of Open Science Pioneers in Serbia on 29 December 2020 (<https://events.ni4os.eu/event/37/>). Along with the basic information about NI4OS-Europe, the updated EOSC Portal was presented to participants. The event also featured discussion on the FAIR principles and repositories. The audience (22 participants) included various Open Science stakeholders: researchers, librarians and institutional decision-makers. It was organized by the University of Belgrade’s NI4OS-Europe team as an online event.

The second dissemination event <https://events.ni4os.eu/event/40/> in Serbia was organized on 24 February 2021 and was attended by institutional decision-makers at the

University of Belgrade. The event was jointly organized by the UoB NI4OS-Europe team and the EOSC co-creation project [Boosting EOSC readiness: Creating a scalable model for capacity building in RDM](#). It focused on FAIR principles, research data management and the related skills and competencies, as well as infrastructure.

NI4OS-Europe national dissemination event in North Macedonia, November 6, 2020

<https://events.ni4os.eu/event/22/>

The National Dissemination Event for North Macedonia was held on November 6th 2020. This event brought together more than 60 participants from various stakeholders including universities, ministries, libraries etc. It was a great opportunity to spread information and raise awareness not only about EOSC, NI4OS-Europe project, Open Science and FAIR data but also National Open Science Cloud Initiatives. The event also included a presentation of the related activities on the development of policies for open access to research infrastructures in the WB6 region. The Q&A session hosted a lively discussion on the presented information, as well as expressions of interest for more in-depth trainings on the presented topics. The dissemination event ended with a highly informative Q&A session. The event triggered great discussions among the participants and expression of interest for more in-depth trainings on the presented topics.

NI4OS-Europe national dissemination event in Montenegro, February 18, 2020

<https://events.ni4os.eu/event/6/>

The first “National Initiatives for Open Science in Europe – NI4OS-Europe” dissemination event in Montenegro was held on February 18th 2020, at Žabljak, in the frame of 24th International Information Technology Conference IT 2020 (www.it.ac.me). IT 2020 conference was organized 18-22 February and it hosted more than 200 participants from all scientific and educational institutions from Montenegro and from the region. The conference is supported by relevant policy makers in the fields of science, education and economics, whose representatives have also participated at the conference.

At the dissemination event, firstly, prof. Enis Kočan, who is NI4OS-Europe team member and NPR for Open Science in Montenegro, has presented main concepts of Open Science. In the second presentation EOSC initiative and services were presented by Lidija Milosavljević, national EOSC promoter. After that, prof. Božo Krstajić, project leader of the UoM NI4OS-Europe team explained main goals of NI4OS-Europe project, undertaken project activities, as well as planned actions at the national and international level. Finally, prof. Milutin Radonjić, UOM NI4OS-Europe team member has presented planned NI4OS-Europe activities in Montenegro, the benefits it can bring to stakeholders and wider scientific community.

The event was announced at the conference website http://www.it.ac.me/eng/display.php?id_l=15 and at the project website <https://events.ni4os.eu/event/6/timetable/#20200218>.

There were 34 attendees at the event. The project caused significant interest and discussion at the dissemination event.

Report on the first dissemination event held in Montenegro was published on NI4OS-Europe website <https://ni4os.eu/2020/04/08/this-happened-in-montenegro-report-of-the-first-dissemination-event/>.

NI4OS-Europe national dissemination event in Armenia, September 28, 2020

<https://events.ni4os.eu/event/14/>

Despite the challenges and lockdowns forced by the pandemic of COVID-19 the NI4OS-Europe national dissemination event in Armenia was held successfully using the online platform.

The Institute of Informatics and Automation Problems (IIAP) of the National Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Armenia, as a partner of NI4OS-Europe Project has organized a national dissemination event on capacity building in the field of open science on September 28, 2020.

After the opening session Shushanik Sargsyan, Head of the Centre for Scientific Information Analysis and Monitoring, IIAP, gave a detailed overview of EOSC and Open Science, the Armenian OpenAire National Open Access Desk (NOAD) organized within NI4OS-Europe (National Initiatives for Open Science in Europe) Project funded by the European Commission under the Horizon 2020 European research infrastructures. The guest speaker Iryna Kuchma, Manager of the EIFL Open Access Programme, has presented OpenAire Research Communities in Europe to Armenian community.

The event was announced in webinar form using the platform: <https://meet.asnet.am/b/hra-fen-y2pat>. The agenda is available on the project event website <https://events.ni4os.eu/event/14/timetable/#20200928>.

NI4OS-Europe national dissemination event in Bosnia and Herzegovina, February 25, 2021

<https://events.ni4os.eu/event/41/>

The event is scheduled on the project agenda system. It will start with a presentation of NI4OS-Europe, EOSC and the country position within the EU and global Open Science area. Then Open Science tools and implementation of satellite photos classification system will be presented, including lessons we learned, overview of tools used for machine learning and web front generation and demonstration of the service in use. The third main presentation is focused on fostering the application of RRI principles at the territorial level in Western Balkans. The event will end with a discussion entitled "How can I benefit from NI4OS-Europe and EOSC?". Concrete examples of available tools and services within the scope of NI4OS-Europe project and their application to ongoing research initiatives will be considered.

2.3.1.2 NI4OS-Europe awareness raising events

Additionally, the project team has also organized several productive meetings to raise awareness in South-East Europe, highlight specific needs and pave the way towards national federation.

Webinar for the Kosovar higher education community, 28 May 2020

On 28 May 2020, NI4OS-Europe project, in collaboration with the KODE project and GEANT partner relations team, organized an online webinar for the Kosovar higher education community, with the aim to give an introduction to the EOSC initiative, and NI4OS-Europe activities with a special focus on the establishment of National Open Science Cloud Initiatives (NOSCI). ATHENA, whose core project activity is the setting up of NOSCI, presented the role of the NOSCI in supporting EOSC in national level, ensuring inclusiveness on European level for enabling Open Science and promoting federation on national level. The event was realized on the NI4OS-Europe webinar platform.

EOSC Governance and Sustainability Workshop, 20 July 2020

In July 2020, ATHENA, as WP2 leader, organized the EOSC Governance and Sustainability Workshop (20 July 2020), an online workshop that brought together project partners and EOSC Governance Board national delegates of the region. The aim of the workshop was to initiate the dialogue on the role and contribution of the NI4OS-Europe project to EOSC through the establishment of NOSCI.

2.3.2. Related dissemination events

2.3.2.1 Large European events

A special attention was given to the main EOSC-related events and to the events held during the Croatian presidency of the Council of the European Union, 1 January 2020 – 31 June 2020. The project NI4OS- Europe was presented at the most relevant events during this period:

EOSC Symposium 2019, 26-28 November 2019, Budapest, Hungary

NI4OS-Europe participated in EOSC Symposium 2019, one of the largest EOSC events, which was held on 26-28 November in Budapest, Hungary. The Symposium brought together stakeholders and all the involved EOSC communities in a 3-day consultation for the implementation of the European Open Science Cloud.

Zoe Cournia, the leader of NI4OS-Europe Life Science community, has delivered a keynote speech on the added value of EOSC services for research. In the FAIR metrics session, Eleni Toli of ATHENA Research Center and NI4OS-Europe Project Director, provided an overview of the project, while on the second day, in the "EOSC as a Federation" plenary session, she talked about the NI4OS-Europe scope, objectives and partnership, the candidate generic & thematic services for on-boarding to EOSC, as well as the short-term roadmap of the project.

EOSC-hub week 2020: Online workshop on Policy landscape across Europe, 20 May 2020

The state and progress of the national Open Science policies and the actions that need to take place for ensuring minimal viable EOSC was the main topic of discussions during the

'Policy landscape across Europe' online workshop that was held on May 20th, 2020, at the EOSC-hub week. A presentation "[The role of NI4OS-Europe in OS Innovation in South-East Europe](#)" was given. The event was co-organized by NI4OS-Europe, EOSC-hub, EOSC-Pillar, EOSC-Nordic, and EOSC Synergy projects.

Advancing R&I ecosystems in the Western Balkans with regard to their ERA integration, 04 September 2020

The future and the challenges in enhancing R&I ecosystems in the Western Balkans for their integration to the European Research Area was discussed in a dedicated [event taking place on 4 September, during ESOF2020](#). NI4OS-Europe was presented to provide input regarding the developments taking place at national and regional level as a crucial step towards the materialization of EOSC. The presentation provided the background of the efforts towards enabling high-quality research and ICT developments and regional cross-border collaboration via the delivery of advanced networking and computational resources, thematic services as well as application support and training to the users. It also emphasized on the importance of maintaining close cooperation with governments to secure national support for EOSC e-Infrastructures and ensuring synergy and complementarity between national, regional and EU actions and funds. Regional initiatives such as NI4OS-Europe are pieces of the puzzle to sustain regional R&D, R&E, ICT development, increasing the retention of talented scientists and engineers in the region, making available the benefits of Information Society and Open Science for all citizens. The event was organized by the European Commission DG Research and Innovation – through its International Service Facility scheme supporting the Western Balkans Steering Platform on Research and Innovation. [The video recording of the session is available online](#).

EOSC Symposium 2020, 19-22 October 2020

NI4OS-Europe was presented at the largest event in 2020 organised by the EOSC Executive & Governance Boards with the support of the EOSC Secretariat project. Anastas Mishev presented NI4OS-Europe within the framework of the session entitled an equitable EOSC: EOSC challenges & opportunities in South Eastern & Eastern Europe. He represented the whole South-East Europe region in this cardinal event. He talked about the excellent project's results that it helped close the digital gap in the region; he promoted the stakeholder map available on our website and shared some details on the Onboarding Task Force activities.

Open Science Fair in Porto OSFair2019, 16-18 Sept. 2019, Portugal

The NI4OS-Europe project was presented by a poster entitled "NI4OS-EUROPE: Building National Initiatives for Open Science in Europe" at Open Science Fair in Porto ([OSFair2019](#), 16-18 Sept. 2019) displaying the NI4OS-Europe roadmap. Namely, it provides an overview of the project's mission and objectives, the core actions to achieve them, the expected outcomes, and the target region.

RDA 16th Plenary Meeting, 9-12 November 2020

The NI4OS-Europe project was presented during the [RDA 16th Plenary Meeting](#), (9-12 November 2020) in a poster about the License Clearance Tool (LCT) [13], an open-source tool which offers platform-assisted license clearance for various resources and addresses legal aspects in FAIR & Open Research Data Management (ORDM). The poster describes the LCT features, assets and the two workflows that it supports.

TF meeting FAIR Assessment and certification of digital objects and data repositories, 26 November 2020

Being an active member of the EOSC Community, NI4OS-Europe participates in the cross-project collaboration among INFRAEOSC-05 projects. On 26 November 2020, the INFRAEOSC-5 FAIR data and infrastructure Task Force online meeting (“FAIR Assessment and certification of digital objects and data repositories”) was a unique opportunity to present to the European Commission the work being carried out in supporting Open and FAIR principles.

Working Group on Open Science, Research and Innovation meeting, 21 January 2020

On 21 January 2020, Biljana Kosanović (UoB), presented the NI4OS-Europe project and early results of the NI4OS-Europe project survey at the Working Group on Open Science, Research and Innovation of the Regional Cooperation Council, in Brussels.

e-IRG workshop, May 2020

The e-IRG workshop addressed top challenges for the further development of e-Infrastructures in the European Research Area and beyond. Workshop was organized within the framework of Croatia's Presidency of the Council of the European Union by the e-IRG Secretariat and the University of Zagreb, the University Computing Centre (SRCE) with the support of the Ministry of Science and Education of the Republic of Croatia. As part of the session Future skills in the new European Research Area, Sonja Filipovska presented NI4OS-Europe project. e-IRG workshop programme is available on the following link: <http://e-irg.eu/workshop-2020-05-programme>.

International conference “Research Infrastructures of the Future” (FUTURIS 2019), 10-11 December, 2019, Bulgaria

The conference was organized as follow-up of the EU Flagship conference on RIs “Research Infrastructures beyond 2020 – sustainable and effective ecosystem for science and society”, 22-23 March 2018, Sofia, organized during the Bulgarian Presidency of the Council of the European Union in March 2018. The event was focused on the synchronization of national and EU efforts towards the next programming period in the context of long-term sustainability of European research and innovation infrastructures. The NI4OS-Europe project was presented.

2.3.2.2 Events in partner countries

Apart from large European events, in each partner country the project team exploited important local events for project dissemination. Thus, NI4OS-Europe has been presented at various events like Open Science Days (in Serbia, Bulgaria, Greece, Cyprus), webinars for scientists and general public (all countries), large scientific conferences (Bulgaria, Croatia), at industrial meetings and university seminars, etc. The most important events are included in the list of events in the Marketing report (section 3).

Greece:

- “OpenAIRE και EOSC: σημεία αλληλεπίδρασης και συμβολή στην Ανοικτή Επιστήμη”: Webinar on interactions and contribution to Open Science supported by OpenAIRE and NI4OS-Europe: <https://www.athenarc.gr/el/events/openaire-eosc-webinar>
- “Διαλειτουργικότητα στο EOSC: εφαρμογή των οδηγιών του OpenAIRE για τα αποθετήρια”: webinar on interoperability, metadata enrichment and usage statistics. The webinar was organised by the National Open Science Desks in Greece and Cyprus in collaboration with N4OS-Europe. It addressed Greek-speaking repository managers.

Cyprus

- Open Science: From Theory to practice on 24/10/2019 (organized by UCY) Presentation of NI4OS-Europe in Greek by A. Athenodorou, http://opensciencecy.ucy.ac.cy/?convert_event=national-oa-week-event-2019.
- 2020 Open Data Day: Transparency, Innovation, Development” 5/3/2020 (Organized by Ministry of Finance and UCY) Presentation of NI4OS-Europe in Greek by S. Koukounidou.
- “Interoperability in EOSC: OpenAIRE Guidelines for repositories” webinar 11th of June 2020.
- Participation at the workshop Research Libraries, Researchers & the EOSC: Multidisciplinary Universities. Presentation entitled: “European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Libraries role and readiness to success” <https://www.knowledge.services/research/research-libraries-researchers-and-the-eosc/w4> / 25th of January 2021.

Bulgaria

- NI4OS-Europe project was presented during the visit of the President of Bulgaria and his team at IICT, 10 December 2019, [link](#).
- NI4OS-Europe was presented in the RDA BG Node Workshop on Data Management, 24 July 2021, <https://rda.bg/en/node/28>.
- NI4OS-Europe presented at the Webinar for Open Science, organized by Sofia University (RDA.bg) on 21 September 2020.
- NI4OS-Europe presented in the 11th National Information Day on Open Access to Scientific Publications, Data and Data Science, Bulgarian Open Science Cloud, 25 September 2020.

- NI4OS-Europe presented in the Annual meeting of the National Centre for HPC and Distributed Computing, 24 July 2020, by the director of the Centre Prof. A. Karaivanova, [link](#).
- Presentations at the webinar Open Science, FAIR data and ORDM, organized by the CoE for Informatics and ICT, 26 November 2020(<http://ict.acad.bg/?p=1133>): A. Karaivanova presented "Open data, Open Science, EOSC", T. Gurov presented "Data and FAIR principles", S. Ivanovska "ORDM".
- NI4OS-Europe was presented at the conference "Scientific Publications, Data and Data Science, Bulgarian Open Science Cloud", Burgas 24-26 September 2020, organized by IMI-BAS (third party in NI4OS-Europe).

Croatia

- In November 2020, the Ministry of Science and Education of the Republic of Croatia granted a mandate to SRCE and with that supported the membership of SRCE in the EOSC Association with the aim of coordinating national initiatives for open science and building the national OSC. *Numerous meetings were organized at the ministry level and were held prior to the decision with the aim to get acquainted with the current status with Open Science Cloud initiative at EU level, to present the opportunities which are opening up to the entire scientific and research community in Croatia through the development of open science and to discuss future national plans.*
- SRCE had created webpage devoted to NI4OS-Europe project in Croatian language (webpage is available on the following link: <https://www.srce.unizg.hr/NI4OS-Europe>) which is constantly updated. Its purpose is to disseminate activities, events and information that promote NI4OS-Europe project within Croatian community.
- SRCE also participated in additional dissemination activities related to translations of official NI4OS-Europe brochure and brochures about EOSC and FAIR. All three brochures were published on SRCE's webpage devoted to NI4OS-Europe project.
- In February 2020 SRCE organized Croatian RDA event in city of Rijeka about research data management which gathered representatives from research community and university libraries. During the event NI4OS-Europe brochure was handout to participants (Rijeka, 2/27/2020, link to program: <https://www.srce.unizg.hr/rda/dogadjaj-rijeka>). Due to pandemic, other three Croatian RDA events were held online: 5/25/2020, 6/1/2020 and 6/26/2020. Information on the NI4OS-Europe project and brochures are provided on all occasions. In order to promote FAIR principles data sharing and re-use of data, SRCE published Research Data Management Handbook intended for Croatian research community.
- OS related presentations at PUBMET 2019 (September 18-20, 2019) and PUBMET2020 (September 16-18 2020) Conference on Scholarly Communication in the Context of Open Science and NI4OS-Europe Capacity Building for Croatia (given by RBI team members).
- Presentation at round table „Obrada podataka i otkrivanje znanja u digitalnoj humanistici“ Eva Cetinić, Davor Davidović, Karolj Skala. Data analysis and knowledge discovery in digital humanities, (Zagreb, February 18, 2020).

- Participating in UNESCO Joint Appeal for Open Sciences - presentation on OS infrastructure for OS in Croatia (and Eastern Europe) and challenges (October 27, 2020).

Hungary:

- HRDA meetup: on 29th June 2020 KIFÜ partner presented about the national initiatives of "[European Open Science Cloud](#)".
- HRDA: for the Hungarian Research Data Alliance Community UD partner [presented NI4OS-Europe](#) on June 29th 2020.
- On the Hungarian Networkshop 2020 event 4 presentations were held in relation with NI4OS-Europe project. First of all there were a workshop section on 2nd September, entitled "[News of Data Management](#)", where UD talked about NI4OS-Europe and its functions, how the regional stakeholders were being mapped, how personas were defined where the Hungarian Networkshop community were channeled and started an important discourse in relation of EOSC and its potentials and services. The other presentation on 2nd September 2020 was about "[European Open Science Cloud](#)" held by KIFÜ. On 3rd of September 2020 UD presented NI4OS-Europe for the Hungarian stakeholders, entitled "[Building an Open Scholarly Ecosystem in Europe](#)". Also, we had the chance to highlight in a presentation entitled "Research Data Management in a University Ecosystem" the use of EOSC and related services.
- "[Library Services in the Changing Data Culture](#)" at EAHIL 16th of November 2020.
- On 20th January 2021 UD presented [How libraries support open science?](#) and how NI4OS-Europe comes into this picture.

Romania:

- NI4OS-Europe information included and promoted in the related event "Open Science landscaping and strategic development in Romania" organized on March 10, 2020 in Bucharest: the event is part of a broader activity of setting a national open science initiative and connecting the Romanian community to the major projects and actions carried at the European level, (NI4OS, OpenAIRE, RDA Europe). Information provided in NI4OS-Europe has been used for the support documents of the event and disseminated to the participants. Also, with the event's occasion, the overall objectives of the NI4OS-Europe project have been promoted.
- Discussed NI4OS-Europe COVID-19 related activities in a webinar with the OS stakeholders on April 14, 2020.
- Meeting Discussions with Romanian Society of Bioinformatics on providing support on ORD for life sciences.
- OS with focus on RDM - October 6th, 2020 (around 240 participants) <https://uefiscdi.gov.ro/open-science-strategic-approaches-and-the-importance-of-open-research-data>.
- First approach to the national cloud projects for scientific data (financed through structural funds) in Romania (exploring EOSC participation) <http://acire20.ifin.ro/> (2020, October 18th meeting).

Slovenia:

NI4OS-Europe was present at several Slovenian national events where the partners disseminated information about NI4OS-Europe, the EOSC and FAIR principles:

- Focus on Open Science Conference (8th November 2019): UMUKM presented the NI4OS-Europe project at the international conference Focus on Open Science on 8th November 2019 in Ljubljana (<http://openctk.com/>). The title of the presentation was "Slovenian initiative for National Open Science Cloud: project NI4OS-Europe and national activities" (<https://youtu.be/izQ6eZYKqtA>).
- RDA Node Slovenia Conference: Scientific Journals and Research Data (28th January 2020). UMUKM gave a presentation at the RDA Node Slovenia Conference: Scientific Journals and Research Data with the title "Overview of Global Practices" on academic publishing, open science and research data management: https://www.rd-alliance.org/system/files/documents/Legat_Pregled_zgledov.pdf.
- Open Research Data and Scientific Excellence (21st April 2020): UMUKM joined a public online discussion about RDM with other important Slovenian open science stakeholders, including policymakers, service providers and researchers. (<https://www.facebook.com/events/260051691833510>).
- Research Data and the European Open Science Cloud Conference (18th June 2020): UMUKM presented digital skills for the European Open Science Cloud and the NI4OS-Europe training methodology, moderated the EOSC session and the round table discussion with Slovenian EOSC delegates at the Slovenian virtual conference Research Data and the European Open Science Cloud (<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3899688>). YouTube: (<https://youtu.be/p7-qdx3Uz8>).
- PubMet 2020 Conference (18th September 2020): UMUKM gave a presentation at the 7th Conference on Scholarly Communication and Publishing in the Context of Open Science PubMet 2020: "Slovenian Research Infrastructure and Open Science – New Challenges". YouTube: https://youtu.be/vY_XHMG9GMI.
- Open Science 2020 Conference (21st October 2020): UMUKM gave a presentation on the infrastructural aspects of open science in Slovenia at the Young Academy Open Science 2020 on-line conference: "Open Science in Slovenia and the European Open Science Cloud": https://libguides.ukm.um.si/ld.php?content_id=33261282. YouTube: https://youtu.be/ZJg3k19_XxE.
- Transferable skills for doctoral students of the University of Maribor (17th November 2020): UMUKM presented the EOSC, the NI4OS-Europe project, the FAIR principles and RDM at the University of Maribor doctoral training „Transferable skills for doctoral students“: https://libguides.ukm.um.si/ld.php?content_id=33315306. YouTube: <https://youtu.be/DpMuwK3GsYE>.
- Open Data & Resources: Slovenian NI4OS-Europe Capacity Building (25th November 2020): UMUKM and ARNES organized a national NI4OS-Europe capacity building: Open Data & Resources. The event focused on the topics: EOSC, FAIR and RDM. <https://events.ni4os.eu/event/23/>. A report of the event was published on the NI4OS-Europe website <https://ni4os.eu/2020/12/24/open-data-resources-slovenian-ni4os-europe-capacity-building/>.

- Biomedical Circle: Open Research Data in Medicine (10th December 2020): UMUKM presented NI4OS-Europe, the EOSC, open science and research data management. <https://youtu.be/ohvYYCakvCM>.
- Research Data Management Support in the Library (27th January 2020): UMUKM presented Open Science, RDM and the FAIR principles training for students and researchers at the workshop, organized by the Slovenian RDA Node, aimed primarily at librarians in higher education and research institutions and other research support staff. https://odprta-knjiznica.si/files/2021/01/Dunja_Legat_RDA_27_1_2021_V2.pd.
- Arnes disseminated information about the EOSC at its annual conference Network of Knowledge (Mreža Znanja) dedicated to informatics and computer science in the fields of education, research and culture which covers systemic aspects of the use of new technologies as well as presentations of good practices. NI4OS-Europe and EOSC were presented by both national EOSC GB representatives, Jan Jona Javoršek and Peter Sterle.

Serbia:

- On 24 October 2020, Vladimir Otašević and Biljana Kosanović (UoB) presented the data visualizations made within the NI4OS-Europe Open Science landscaping activity at the third conference Application of Free Software and Open Hardware, organized in a hybrid format at the Faculty of Electrical Engineering, University of Belgrade, Serbia (<https://ni4os.eu/2020/10/27/ni4os-europe-open-science-landscape-survey-data-visualizations-presented-at-the-pssoh-conference/>). A conference paper has also been published: <https://zenodo.org/communities/pssoh2020/?page=1&size=20>.
- The RePol development team from UoB will present the repository policy generator developed under WP4 at a webinar organized by EIFL on 17 February 2021. The target audience is repository managers from all over the world.
- During 2020, UoB team members participated in many online conferences, webinars and workshops, where they had an opportunity to mention the activities and results of NI4OS-Europe in discussions during breakout sessions (e.g. FAIRsFAIR's FAIR Competences for Higher Education Design Workshop; OpenAIRE Week, OPERAS Conference, International FAIR Convergence Symposium, etc.).
- Brief updates about NI4OS-Europe activities are included in regular training sessions for librarians and repository managers (12 training sessions were held in the second half of 2020).
- Biljana Kosanović presented the NI4OS-Europe landscaping activity at the EOSC-Pillar webinar on 11 October 2019: <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/events/webinar-coming-together-map-national-landscape-analysis-eosc-between-5-relevant-projects>.
- Along with conventional training sessions, NI4OS-Europe National Capacity Building Training in Serbia, organized on 6 November 2020, as part of the third edition of Open Science Days, focused on the promotion of the tools developed by the NI4OS-Europe project team (NI4OS-Europe Catalogue, License Clearance Tool, repository policy generator, and NI4OS-Europe vs. COVID-19; <https://ni4os.eu/2020/11/17/ni4os-europe-national-capacity-building-training-in-serbia-6-november-2020/>). The audience included 64 participants.

- Instead of organizing one dissemination event that would gather a large audience, the UoB team decided to organize several smaller events, more suitable for an online environment, targeting particular stakeholder groups.

Bosnia and Herzegovina:

- Open Access to Research Infrastructure: Principles and Policy Development (June 30th 2020).
- Meeting on Researcher Network Data Archive for Social Sciences in Bosnia and Herzegovina (July 14th 2020).
- Consultation on synergies between Horizon and European structural and investment funds in EOSC Partnership webinar (July 20th 2020).
- Open Consultation for EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (July 28th 2020).
- Open Science and Intellectual Property Rights, September 25, 2020 at the University of Banja Luka (EURAXESS). Presentation of NI4OS-Europe project and EOSC was given.
- FAIR Competences for Higher Education Design Workshop (October 8th and 9th 2020).
- EOSC Association Bylaws: basic principles & open consultation DAY (October 20th 2020).
- OpenAIRE AMKE GA (November 2nd and 3rd 2020).

Moldova:

- NI4OS-Europe Open Science Landscape Survey was presented within the round table "Open Access – Equity in research environment, organized by the REM Consortium and the Department of Communication and Information Theory of the Faculty of Journalism and Communication Sciences of the Moldova State University (October 25, 2019). The event was attended by representatives of 21 organizations from the Republic of Moldova.
- Dr. Peter Bogatencov made presentation "NI4OS: European Open Science Cloud Initiative – Support of Open Science in the South Eastern Europe" at the Round Table "Problems of Open Science in the Republic of Moldova", co-organized by RENAM in cooperation with the Information Society Development Institute, the Academy of Economic Studies of Moldova and Consortium REM (December 12, 2019). The event was attended by representatives of 45 organizations from the Republic of Moldova.
- Dr. Natalia Cheradi presented information about NI4OS-Europe Open Science Landscape Survey results and other project activities at the meeting of the Council of Library Association of Moldova (April 7, 2020).
- Open Science related issues were presented at online round table "Open Access – building structural equity and inclusion", organized by REM Consortium, National Library Association of the Republic of Moldova in collaboration with the Department of Communication and Information Theory of the Faculty of Journalism and Communication Sciences of Moldova State University and the Scientific Library of the Academy of Economic Studies of Moldova (October 21, 2020) <https://eifloamoldova.wordpress.com:>

- Open Science related issues were presented at the Science Days, 3rd edition, organized by the National Library of the Republic of Moldova (November 5, 2020). Presentation by Nelly Țurcan "[Access to information \(content\) and open licenses](#)" (in Romanian).
- NI4OS-Europe activities and project impact were promoted at the European Researchers' Night 2020 online event in Moldova (November 27, 2020).

Georgia:

- On December 22, 2020 online conference took place within the frames of Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation of Georgia project NFR 17-548: "Study of some climate characteristic parameters variability over the territory of Georgia based on regional climate prediction modeling ensemble system". The conference was organized by the Institute of Applied Mathematics of the Tbilisi State University, Georgian Research and Educational Networking Association GRENA and National Environmental Agency. The conference was concluded with interesting discussions among the participants. <https://www.grena.ge/eng/380>.

2.3.3. Media presence

During this period, active dissemination through various channels has emerged as the principal approach for building awareness and community support. Social media outreach has been central in NI4OS-Europe's activities for communicating project outcomes and activities and has been achieved through active participation on different platforms (Twitter, Facebook and Instagram). Embracing Open Access/Science principles, the team created a community on Zenodo to deposit and disseminate projects deliverables and outputs. Last but not least, participating in EOSC-relevant initiatives, Task Forces and Working Groups, the Cross Projects Collaboration Board (CPCB), and national, provided additional communication channels for promoting NI4OS-Europe efforts and outputs.

In addition to the establishment of communication channels, the team has been heavily involved in the production of dissemination content. The project team produced several blog posts dedicated on project activities with a special focus on WP2 and WP4 developments, which were made available through NI4OS-Europe [media corner](#) and organisation's website. The team also populated the project wiki page with COVID-19 resources and information on the [License Clearance Tool \(LCT\)](#) and [Registry Policy Generator \(RePol\)](#) tool. Besides the creation of new content, another important communication activity is to create digestible and ready-to-use information. For example, to ease the access to information regarding the establishment of the National Open Science Cloud Initiatives (NOSCI), content from D2.2 [15] was transformed into easy-to-use tools (checklists) in a brochure format. These checklists are already available to project partners through the NI4OS-Europe document repository system (Box) and will soon be publicly available on the project website.

NI4OS-Europe start was announced with the completion of its kick-off meeting that took place in Athens on 8-10 October 2019. The announcement entitled "NI4OS-Europe kick off meeting sets the priorities for the 1st year of the project implementation" was uploaded on the [project website](#) and disseminated via NI4OS-Europe [Facebook](#) and [Twitter](#) accounts.

NI4OS-Europe accounts on Twitter, Facebook and Instagram.

Twitter: @NI4OS

The NI4OS-Europe twitter account has been active since the beginning of the project. Members of the project partnership have been assigned a role as NI4OS-Europe twitter ambassadors, for promoting project updates and relative to the community tweets, in cooperation with the social media administrators. The main hashtags promoted via the project account are: #NI4OS_eu, #NI4OS, #EOSC, #OpenScience, #FAIR.

- Followers: 543.
- Mentions: 257.
- Profile visits: 2911.

Figure 22: Attendance analysis of NI4OS-Europe Twitter account

Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/NI4OS/>

The project Facebook account has been set up to support further the project communication and marketing activities, and maximize the project outreach.

The account follows the style of the project website to reflect effectively NI4OS-Europe brand identity. The main hashtags promoted via the project account are: #NI4OS_eu, #NI4OS, #EOSC, #OpenScience, #FAIR.

- Followers: 276.
- Posts: 136.
- Total page likes from December 2019 to January 2021: 242.

Figure 23: Attendance analysis of NI4OS-Europe Facebook account

Figure 24: Average performance over time of liked Facebook pages

Instagram: @ni4os.eu

NI4OS-Europe has set up an Instagram account, which is one of the most popular among young users, to increase visibility. However, due to GDPR regulations and the fact that it constitutes an entirely visual platform, its use has been limited.

Figure 25: NI4OS-Europe Instagram account

Dissemination through partner's social media accounts

Apart from using the NI4OS-Europe accounts on Twitter, Facebook and Instagram, some partners use also their organization accounts for project dissemination. Here, for example, we present the list of publications of one of the project partners, SRCE (Croatia), on SRCE's social media channels on Twitter, Facebook and LinkedIn:

- Posting information on Twitter (number of audience reached: 3790):
 - Disseminating webpage of NI4OS-Europe on social media (2/27/2020): <https://twitter.com/SrceHr/status/1232964083684651009?s=20>.
 - about Train the Trainers event *EOSC promotors* (3/20/2020): <https://twitter.com/SrceHr/status/1240975343030341633?s=20>.
 - about e-IRG Workshop (5/4/2020): <https://twitter.com/SrceHr/status/1257233406989078528?s=20>.
 - about Train the Trainers webinars *On-boarding* (6/8/2020): <https://twitter.com/SrceHr/status/1269960383881719810?s=20>.
 - about EOSC Governance and Sustainability: NI4OS-Europe meets the EOSC GB country delegates workshop (7/9/2020): <https://twitter.com/SrceHr/status/1281224978810261506?s=20>.
 - about NI4OS-Europe survey results related with Open Science (8/10/2020): <https://twitter.com/SrceHr/status/1292740654343360517?s=20>.
 - about webinar "*How to Host a Successful Virtual Event training*" (9/2/2020): <https://twitter.com/SrceHr/status/1301087231965265920?s=20>.
 - about webinar/training *FitSM - Light approach to IT Service Management* (9/21/2020): <https://twitter.com/SrceHr/status/1308037662473936896?s=20>.

- about NI4OS-Europe VS COVID initiative (12/11/2020):
<https://twitter.com/SrceHr/status/1337357276995317761?s=20>.
- Posting information on Facebook (number of audience reached: 3395):
 - about Train the Trainers event *EOSC promotori* (3/20/2020):
<https://www.facebook.com/srce.hr/posts/10159644187844498>.
 - about e-IRG Workshop (5/4/2020):
<https://www.facebook.com/srce.hr/posts/10159856994249498>.
 - about Train the Trainers webinars *On-boarding* (6/8/2020):
<https://www.facebook.com/srce.hr/posts/10159998526284498>.
 - about EOSC Governance and Sustainability: NI4OS-Europe meets the EOSC GB country delegates workshop (7/9/2020):
<https://www.facebook.com/srce.hr/posts/10160121014544498>.
 - about NI4OS-Europe survey results related with Open Science (8/10/2020):
<https://www.facebook.com/srce.hr/posts/10160232875584498>.
 - about webinar *How to Host a Successful Virtual Event training* (9/2/2020):
<https://www.facebook.com/srce.hr/posts/10160307341334498>.
 - about webinar/training *FitSM - Light approach to IT Service Management* (9/21/2020):
<https://www.facebook.com/srce.hr/posts/10160367833864498>.
 - about NI4OS-Europe VS COVID initiative (12/11/2020):
<https://www.facebook.com/srce.hr/posts/10160611330799498>.
- Posting information on LinkedIn (number of audience reached: 1925):
 - about Train the Trainers event *EOSC promotori* (3/20/2020):
https://www.linkedin.com/posts/srce_eosc-data-made-in-europe-activity-6646741292967694336-H24J.
 - about e-IRG workshop (5/4/2020):
https://www.linkedin.com/posts/srce_poziv-e-irg-radionica-o-glavnim-izazovima-activity-6662999285900148736-ce2j.
 - about Train the Trainers webinars *On-boarding* (6/8/2020):
https://www.linkedin.com/posts/srce_procesi-integracije-servisa-i-repozitorija-activity-6675726245726035968-Hp4.
 - about EOSC Governance and Sustainability: NI4OS-Europe meets the EOSC GB country delegates workshop (7/9/2020):
https://www.linkedin.com/posts/srce_online-radionica-ni4os-europe-partnera-i-activity-6686989947217444864--rb9.
 - about NI4OS-Europe survey results related with Open Science (8/10/2020): https://www.linkedin.com/posts/srce_otvorena-znanost-koliko-o-njoj-znamo-i-activity-6698505591771426816-k2QG.
 - about webinar *How to Host a Successful Virtual Event training* (9/2/2020):
https://www.linkedin.com/posts/srce_ni4os-europe-activity-6706852345025851392-faep.
 - about webinar/training *FitSM - Light approach to IT Service Management* (9/21/2020): https://www.linkedin.com/posts/srce_odr%C5%BEan-posljednji-ni4os-europe-train-the-activity-6713802503370088448--Cze.
 - about NI4OS-Europe VS COVID initiative (12/11/2020):
https://www.linkedin.com/posts/srce_pokrenuta-inicijativa-ni4os-europe-vs-covid-activity-6743122120424886272-Oace.

Dissemination through local websites

Next, most of the partners publish NI4OS-Europe articles/news on their local websites. Here we list some of them:

(GRNET)

- [Έντεκα εθνικοί Ακαδημαϊκοί και Ερευνητικοί οργανισμοί και εικοσιέξι εθνικές και ευρωπαϊκές υποδομές και πρωτοβουλίες συνεργαστήκαν για τη συγγραφή του Εθνικού Σχεδίου Ανοικτής Επιστήμης για την Ελλάδα.](#)
- [Press release distributed to the media, in Greek: "Πλατφόρμα ανοικτών ψηφιακών πόρων και υπηρεσιών από το έργο NI4OS-Europe".](#)
- [Press Release, "EC funded NI4OS-Europe project contributes to the vision of the European Open Science Cloud, delivering its first integrated resources on its platform".](#)
- [https://grnet.gr/en/2020/11/30/ni4os-europe-newsletter-issue-no-3-november-2020/.](https://grnet.gr/en/2020/11/30/ni4os-europe-newsletter-issue-no-3-november-2020/)
- [https://grnet.gr/en/2020/07/31/ni4os-europe-newsletter-issue-no-2-july-2020/.](https://grnet.gr/en/2020/07/31/ni4os-europe-newsletter-issue-no-2-july-2020/)
- [https://grnet.gr/en/2020/04/30/ni4os-europe-newsletter-issue-no-1-april-2020/.](https://grnet.gr/en/2020/04/30/ni4os-europe-newsletter-issue-no-1-april-2020/)
- [NI4OS-Europe is featured on GRNET website under the projects category, in Greek and English.](#)
- NI4OS-Europe training event in Greece was published on the GRNET website: <https://grnet.gr/en/2021/01/20/ni4os-europe-training-event-in-greece-developing-fair-and-eosc-skills/>
- NI4OS-Europe training event in Greece was published on EuroCC@Greece website: <https://eurocc-greece.gr/ni4os-europe-training-event-in-greece-developing-fair-and-eosc-skills/>

(ATHENA)

- [OpenAIRE και EOOSC: σημεία αλληλεπίδρασης και συμβολή στην Ανοικτή Επιστήμη.](#)
- [EOOSC Governance and Sustainability: NI4OS-Europe meets the EOOSC GB country delegates.](#)

(UCY)

- [http://opensciencecy.ucy.ac.cy/?convert_event=national-oa-week-event-2019.](http://opensciencecy.ucy.ac.cy/?convert_event=national-oa-week-event-2019)
- [http://enewsletter.ucy.ac.cy/.](http://enewsletter.ucy.ac.cy/)
- [http://opensciencecy.ucy.ac.cy/?convert_service=ni4os.](http://opensciencecy.ucy.ac.cy/?convert_service=ni4os)

(IICT)

- About national dissemination event in Bulgaria [http://www.hpc.acad.bg/2020/11/ni4os-national-dissemination-event-in-bulgaria-20-november-2020/.](http://www.hpc.acad.bg/2020/11/ni4os-national-dissemination-event-in-bulgaria-20-november-2020/)
- About national training event in Bulgaria [http://www.hpc.acad.bg/2020/07/invitation-to-participate-at-the-ni4os-training-22-july-2020/.](http://www.hpc.acad.bg/2020/07/invitation-to-participate-at-the-ni4os-training-22-july-2020/)

- About priority access to resources due to COVID-19
<http://www.bas.bg/2020/03/10/бан-представи-иновации-за-борба-с-коро/>.

(SRCE, RBI)

- about Train the Trainers event *EOSC promoters* (3/20/2020):
<https://www.srce.unizg.hr/vijesti/eosc-data-made-europe/objav2020-03-20>.
- announcement about e-IRG Workshop (5/4/2020):
<https://www.srce.unizg.hr/vijesti/poziv-e-irg-radionica-o-glavnim-izazovima-razvoja-europskog-istrazivackog-prostora/objav2020-05-04>.
- about Train the Trainers webinars *On-boarding* (6/8/2020):
<https://www.srce.unizg.hr/vijesti/procesi-integracije-servisa-i-repozitorija-u-sklopu-projekta-ni4os-europe/objav2020-06-08>.
- about EOSC Governance and Sustainability: NI4OS-Europe meets the EOSC GB country delegates workshop (9/7/2020):
<https://www.srce.unizg.hr/vijesti/online-radionica-ni4os-europe-partnera-i-eosc-gb-delegata/objav2020-07-09>.
- about NI4OS-Europe survey results about Open Science (8/10/2020):
<https://www.srce.unizg.hr/vijesti/otvorena-znanost-koliko-o-njoj-znamo-i-sto-ocekujemo/objav2020-08-10>.
- about webinar *How to Host a Successful Virtual Event training* (9/2/2020):
<https://www.srce.unizg.hr/vijesti/savjeti-za-organiziranje-uspjesnog-online-dogadanja/objav2020-09-02>.
- about webinar/training *FitSM - Light approach to IT Service Management* (9/21/2020): <https://www.srce.unizg.hr/vijesti/posljednji-ni4os-europe-train-trainer-webinar/objav2020-09-21>.
- about NI4OS-Europe VS COVID initiative (12/11/2020):<https://www.srce.unizg.hr/vijesti/pokrenuta-inicijativa-ni4os-europe-vs-covid-19/objav2020-12-11>.
- An article about Train the Trainer webinars *ORDM* (no. 80, p.13):https://www.srce.unizg.hr/files/srce/docs/o-srcu/Srce-novosti/srce_novosti_-_broj_80.pdf.
- An article about onboarding two Croatian repositories (no. 81, p.8):
<https://www.srce.unizg.hr/vijesti/izasle-su-srce-novosti-br-81/objav2020-10-15>.
- An article about D2.2 survey results (no. 81, p.9):<https://www.srce.unizg.hr/vijesti/izasle-su-srce-novosti-br-81/objav2020-10-15>.

(KIFÜ, DE)

In Hungary there are two online channels we use to reach the stakeholders and infrastructural community of the country. One of them is the [openscience.hu](https://www.openscience.hu) national informational website, the other one is the [instantscience.hu](https://www.instantscience.hu) blog that we use in collaboration with the HUNOR consortia to reach out to the higher educational/university infrastructural communities and provide them with information on NI4OS-Europe and news on EOSC. OpenScience.hu also has a [Facebook page](#) where we actively share NI4OS-Europe related social media posts. KIFÜ created a microsite about the NI4OS-Europe project via KIFÜ's website It provides information on the project and the related cooperation possibilities and has a news section, as well. <https://kifu.gov.hu/ni4os/hirek>.

(ICI, UEFISCDI)

- A short presentation of the NI4OS-Europe project on the ICI Bucharest site (in Romanian and English) is available at <https://www.ici.ro/ni4os/>.
- Ensuring a constant community approach through constant dissemination of news and relevant information (through the OS Hub RO channels: website, social media, newsletter). <https://uefiscdi.gov.ro/national-initiatives-for-open-science-ni4os>
<https://uefiscdi.gov.ro/noutati-open-science>.
- Dissemination of information regarding NI4OS-Europe survey through the OS HUB Romania communication channels. Also, community reaches in a detailed article on the OS strategic development and the NI4OS-Europe involvement through a dedicated article the Romanian Market Watch magazine <https://uefiscdi.gov.ro/news-uefiscdi-si-stewardship-ul-pentru-stiinta-deschisa-open-science-knowledge-hub-romania>.

(ARNES, UМУKM)

The partners use their social media channels to disseminate news and information, but information about the NI4OS-Europe project and EOSC has also been disseminated via various web sites as well, a few examples are listed below:

- Project announcement in the University of Maribor news section (27/09/2019) <https://www.um.si/univerza/medijsko-sredisce/novice/Strani/novice.aspx?p=2871>.
- University of Maribor Library Open Access LibGuide News section <https://libguides.ukm.um.si/odprimoUM/novice>.
- Eurodoc: Open Science in Slovenia: report on Conference on Open Research Data and workshop (14/01/2020): <http://www.eurodoc.net/news/2020/open-science-in-slovenia-report-on-conference-on-open-research-data-and-workshop>.
- Metina lista: European Open Science Cloud (29/06/2020): <https://metinalista.si/evropski-oblak-odprte-znanosti/>.
- Slovenian Press Agency: Online Conference Open Science 2020 (19/10/2020): <https://krog.sta.si/2821224/z-nacrtom-s-zacetek-spletne-odprte-znanosti>.
- Online poster for Open Access Week 2020 (October 2020) https://libguides.ukm.um.si/ld.php?content_id=33241177.
- National capacity building announcement for RDA in Slovenia (22/11/2020) <https://www.rd-alliance.org/group/rda-slovenia/post/vabilo-na-dogodek-odprti-podatki-zmogljivosti>.

(IPB, RCUB-UOB)

- The information about the establishment of the national Team for Open Science in Serbia, which plays a crucial role in the process of establishing a NOSCI in Serbia, was prepared by the UoB team and published on the NI4OS-Europe and OpenAIRE websites <https://www.openaire.eu/blogs/aligning-the-development-of-open-science-in-serbia-with-european-initiatives>, as well as on the website of the Serbian Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development

(<http://www.mpn.gov.rs/razvoj-otvorene-nauke-u-srbiji-u-skladu-sa-inciјativama-u-evropi/>).

- The NI4OS-Europe stakeholder map and survey results were prepared by the UoB team for publishing on the NI4OS-Europe website and a blog post was written: <https://ni4os.eu/2020/03/23/ni4os-europe-open-science-stakeholder-map-now-available-online/>. The data underlying the stakeholder map were published in Zenodo as an open dataset: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3722929>.
- The information about the NI4OS-Europe National Capacity Building Training event was disseminated through blog posts on the NI4OS-Europe website and an announcement on the national Open Science Platform in Serbia: <http://open.ac.rs/vesti?id=be1f99d6e4893b19f3ca39fde5a4fd66>. The event was also briefly covered in a blog post on the OpenAIRE website: <https://www.openaire.eu/blogs/open-science-days-in-serbia-iii>.
- During the summer of 2020, NI4OS-Europe promotional materials were translated into Serbian. The translated materials were uploaded on the national open Science portal in Serbia: [http://open.ac.rs/svevesti/be1f99d6e4893b19f3ca39fde5a4fd66/RS-NI4OS%20-%20FAIR\(1\).pdf](http://open.ac.rs/svevesti/be1f99d6e4893b19f3ca39fde5a4fd66/RS-NI4OS%20-%20FAIR(1).pdf), <http://open.ac.rs/vesti?id=be1f99d6e4893b19f3ca39fde5a4fd66>. During the Open Science Days Conference (5-6 November 2020), the links to these materials were delivered to participants.
- In January 2021, the information about RePol was disseminated through the CORE Ambassadors and EIFL mailing lists.
- Posts published on the NI4OS-Europe website, as well as other news related to NI4OS-Europe are regularly tagged for inclusion in the Open Access Tagging Project database (Milica Ševkušić is a volunteer for OATP): https://tagteam.harvard.edu/hubs/oatp/item_search?q=oa.ni4os. OATP pushes tagged information to Twitter and to thousands of feed subscribers.

(UniBL)

- <https://www.unibl.org/sr/vesti/2020/09/uspjesno-realizovan-projekat-edukativni-moduli-o-zastiti-intelektualnog-vlasnistva>.

(UOM)

- NI4OS-Europe project, its main goals and activities to be conducted at the national level in Montenegro, have been described in the Montenegrin strategic document on Open Science, entitled "Programme of Implementation of Open Science Principles in Montenegro with the Action Plan (2020–2022)", which was adopted by the Government of Montenegro, on June 25, 2020. Both version of this document (in Montenegrin and in English) can be found at the website of the former Ministry of Science of Montenegro <https://www.mna.gov.me/en/ministry?alphabet=lat>, which has now become part of the Ministry of Education, Science, Culture and Sport.
- Information about adoption of this strategic document was also published at the NI4OS/Europe website <https://ni4os.eu/2020/06/25/government-of-montenegro-has-adopted-the-first-strategic-document-related-to-open-science/>.

- NI4OS-Europe project was informally disseminated during organization and in the frame of the first national capacity building event, held online on October 27, 2020 (<https://events.ni4os.eu/event/20/>). The electronic version of project brochure, as well as translated brochures on EOSC and FAIR principles, have been distributed to all participants of this training event.

(RENAM)

- On December 10, 2019 the Round Table "Problems of Open Science in the Republic of Moldova" to be held on December 12, 2019 was announced on RENAM website (in Romanian) <https://renam.md/renamnews/masa-rotunda-probleme-ale-stiintei-deschise-in-republica-moldova/>.
- On December 16, 2019 a wrap-up article about Round Table "Problems of Open Science in the Republic of Moldova", which took place on December 12, 2019, was published on RENAM website (in English and Romanian) <https://renam.md/renamnews/stiinta-deschisa-provocari-si-obiective-de-dezvoltare-in-republica-moldova/>.
- On June 8, 2020 NI4OS-Europe Fast Access Channel to its services, tools and software for the scientific communities to tackle COVID-19 was announced on RENAM website (in English and Romanian) <https://renam.md/renamnews/apply-and-gain-fast-track-access-to-ni4os-europe-resources/>.
- On August 24, 2020 open registration for the NI4OS-Europe National Capacity Building Training Event in the Domain of Open Science for Moldova to be held on September 24, 2020 was announced on RENAM website (in English, Romanian and Russian) <https://renam.md/renamnews/2117/>.
- On September 29, 2020 a wrap-up article about the NI4OS-Europe National Capacity Building Training Event in the Domain of Open Science for Moldova, which took place on September 24, 2020, was published on RENAM website (in English, Romanian and Russian) <https://renam.md/renamnews/the-first-ni4os-europe-national-capacity-building-training-event-successfully-took-place-in-moldova/>.
- On November 26, 2020 information about the European Researchers' Night in the Republic of Moldova and RENAM participation in this online event was published on RENAM website (in English and Romanian) <https://renam.md/renamnews/noaptea-cercetatorilor-europeni-2020/>.

(GRENA)

- Providing cloud infrastructure for the 4th European Junior Olympiad in Informatics held on 2-6 of September 2020 <https://www.grena.ge/eng/372>.
- Supporting 3 projects of National Science Foundation of Georgia in usage of GRENA cloud infrastructure <https://eapconnect.eu/stories/climate-projects-funded-by-shota-rustaveli-foundation-use-grena-cloud-infrastructure/>
- On November 25, 2020 GRENA hosted the National Capacity Building NI4OS-Europe training in Georgia <https://www.grena.ge/eng/379>.
- News regarding GRENA hosting the National Capacity Building NI4OS-Europe training was published on Connect Online magazine <https://connect.geant.org/2020/12/16/grena-hosts-open-science-training-event-for-georgian-research-and-education>.

- Information regarding the National Capacity Building NI4OS-Europe training was also published on eapconnect.eu web page: <https://prod.eapconnect.eu/stories/grena-hosts-open-science-training-event-for-georgian-research-and-education/>.
- Two Twitter posts were created at GRENA's twitter account about the National Capacity Building NI4OS-Europe training; One during the event: <https://twitter.com/GRENA/status/1331533740095533062> and another one after the event: <https://twitter.com/GRENA/status/1339496573672312835>.

Journals, Magazines, Newsletters

(GRNET)

NI4OS-Europe press release, "[EC funded NI4OS-Europe project contributes to the vision of the European Open Science Cloud, delivering its first integrated resources on its platform](#)", issued on 15/02/2021, announces the on-boarding of 19 new services to the project digital service catalogue and its current status. The on-boarding is presented as part of the project multi-level activities to set a strong foundation for the implementation of the EOSC, with benefits for a wide range of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) scientists and professionals. The press release was sent to all partners and was disseminated via their national channels. Indicatively, in Greece it was published on the following news portals and newsletters:

- [Epixeiro.](#)
- [iNEWS.](#)
- [Startupper.](#)
- [ICTplus.](#)
- [Techpress.](#)
- NET FAX and COM TODAY newsletters (only available in printed version).
- [MOVED.](#)

A more detailed announcement was disseminated through the [NI4OS-Europe website](#), [Facebook](#), [Twitter](#) and [Instagram](#) accounts.

(SRCE)

- Published article in Srce novosti about NI4OS-Europe deliverable D4.1. Incentives for supporting ORDM and FAIR (RBI task leader Bojan Macan) (See Appendix B).
- Pubmet2020 conference review in EURASLIC Newsletter includes overview on webinar „NI4OS-Europe National Capacity Building Training for Croatia“.
- Article in HKD Novosti mentioned participation of RBI in NI4OS-Europe project (See Appendix B).
- Article regarding open access „David among Goliaths: Open access publishing in scientific (semi-) periphery / Bojan Macan, Lea Škorić, Jelka Petrak“ published in Learned Publishing was chosen in top OA articles published in 2020 and included in Learned Publishing OA Week 2020 Collection. As the article together with CROSBIO COVID-19 hub attracted wide attention, therefore RBI EOSC promotor gave several interviews. As a consequence, articles regarding Open Science, EOSC and NI4OS-Europe project were published in many Croatian national newspapers and on dozen news national portals.

(RENAM)

The following articles, related to DICOM Network service were published:

- Alexandr Golubev, Petru Bogatencov, Grigore Secieru, Ecaterina Matenco "Incident Handling and Personal Data Protection in Medical Images systems", Proceedings of the Workshop on Intelligent Information Systems (WIIS2020), December 4-5, 2020, Chisinau, Republic of Moldova.
- Alexandr Golubev "DICOM image optimization for CLOUD solutions, Open science platforms and mobile systems", Proceedings of the Workshop on Intelligent Information Systems (WIIS2020), December 4-5, 2020, Chisinau, Republic of Moldova.
- Alexandr Golubev "DICOM Network Implementation and Usage in the context of the COVID-19 Pandemic" to be published in March 2021 in the "Archives of the Balkan Medical Union", ISSN 1584-9244, <https://umbalk.org/>.

Radio, TV, videos

- (GRNET) NI4OS-Europe was presented during ESOF2020 dedicated session "Advancing R&I ecosystems in the Western Balkans with regard to their ERA integration" (https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lfHw3aSHiPw&feature=youtu.be&ab_channel=FondazioneInternazionaleTriesteFIT).
- (RBI) RBI EOSC promotor participated in the TV show about science talking about Open Science on the national TV. NI4OS-Europe as well as EOSC, FAIR data principles and OS through is also promoted through contacts with researchers and other stakeholders.
- (IICT) "Change" is 40-minutes film for IICT-BAS, broadcast on national television channels: BNT1 (15.11.2020) and BNT2 (03.10.2020). It presents all the activities of the institute, including the activities of the NI4OS-Europe project. Available in YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HDyKKZADTBk&feature=youtu.be>.
- (UB) Biljana Kosanović presented the project, the state-of-the-art and the survey results at the EOSC-hub Week 2020, on 20 May 2020: <https://www.eosc-hub.eu/eosc-hub-week-2020/agenda/national-policy-developments-supporting-eosc-implementation> (video: <https://youtu.be/5kZLkGbWtpY>).
- (DE) Judit Fazekas-Paragh presented the project and it's innovations at the EOSC-hub Week 2020, on 20 May 2020: <https://www.eosc-hub.eu/eosc-hub-week-2020/agenda/innovation-eosc-regional-projects> (video: <https://youtu.be/tbPT8qseZMM>).
- (ARNES) SLING and the HPC Operation, presentation by Jan Jona Javoršek, Network of Knowledge 2019 (4th December 2019). (Video: <https://video.arnes.si/portal/asset.zul?id=C1ITUGYOHLbgoWNIRHDfrxYm&jwsour ce=cl>).
- (ARNES) The European Open Science Cloud – EOSC, presentation by Peter Sterle, Network of Knowledge 2020 (25th November 2020): (Video: <https://video.arnes.si/portal/asset.zul?id=e9LSkUmZYGEXZWOOAZQOvrn&jwsour ce=cl>).
- (UMUKM) Slovenian initiative for a National Open Science Cloud: project NI4OS-Europe and national activities, presentation by Dunja Legat, Focus on Open Science (8th November 2019). (Video: <https://youtu.be/izQ6eZYKqtA>).
- (UMUKM) Digital skills for the European Open Science Cloud, presentation by Dunja Legat, RDA Node Slovenia Conference: Research Data and the European Open Science Cloud, 18th June 2020. (Video: <https://youtu.be/p7-qdx3Uz8>).

- (UMUKM) Slovenian research infrastructure and open science – new challenges, presentation by Dunja Legat, PubMet 2020, 18th September 2020 (Video: https://youtu.be/vY_XHMG9GMI).
- (UMUKM) Open science in Slovenia and the European Open Science Cloud, presentation by Dunja Legat, Open Science 2020, 21st October 2020 (Video: https://youtu.be/ZJg3k19_XxE).
- (UMUKM) Research Data Management, Transferable skills for doctoral students of the University of Maribor course, presentation by Dunja Legat, 17th November 2020 (Video: <https://youtu.be/DpMuwK3GsYE>).
- (UMUKM) EOSC – The European Open Science Cloud, presentation by Dunja Legat, Biomedical Circle: Open Research Data in Medicine, 10th December 2020 (Video: <https://youtu.be/ohvYYCakvCM>).
- (UMUKM) Open:UM for research data: an example of training at the University of Maribor, presentation by Dunja Legat, Research Data Management Support in Libraries, 27th January 2021. (Video: <https://youtu.be/4U1IDXrqF5w>).

2.4. Collaboration with other initiatives and projects

One of the first results of the collaboration with the other INFRAEOSC projects was the creation of six Task Forces, which are working on specific topics.

- Communications and Events: Aligning EOSC-related common messaging through information sharing between projects and mutual sharing of project news & results.
- FAIR: Reviewing and standardizing FAIR policies and guidelines in order to enable FAIR-aligned services and repositories.
- Landscaping: Defining common targets and methodology for the National Initiatives landscaping activities.
- National Policies and Governance: Collating, discussing and engaging with policymakers and national policies to foster the uptake of Open Science OS practices.
- Service On-boarding: Discussing procedures and solutions to facilitate the flow of services stemming from involved projects into the EOSC Service Catalogue.
- Training and Skills: Synchronising information by establishing shared training resources and common training events.

The delegates from NI4OS-Europe are actively taking part in the task forces in order to maximize community outreach and engagement, across all geographical regions. The collaboration aims to bring greater awareness to the different stakeholder groups, involved in EOSC and help in the implementation of EOSC, the uptake of FAIR and OS.

Thanks to the joint effort of the regional projects a position paper on EOSC – “Insights from Regional Projects & Infrastructures” has been created and deposited in Zenodo. <https://zenodo.org/record/3831561#.YBkPgOhKg2w>.

During the given period we have actively promoted EOSC, OS and FAIR related events within our social media channels, aiming to reach the different target communities. We were also involved in various workshops and trainings, and co-organized some of them:

- EOSC-hub week 2019: Extending and consolidating the EOSC offering: the regional views (<https://www.eosc-hub.eu/sites/default/files/NI4OS.pdf>)
- EOSC-hub week 2020: Online workshop on Policy landscape across Europe (<https://ni4os.eu/2020/05/21/eoschub-week-2020-online-workshop-on-policy-landscape-across-europe/>).
- EOSC-hub week 2020: Online workshop on Innovation from the EOSC regional projects (<https://www.eosc-hub.eu/eosc-hub-week-2020/agenda/innovation-eosc-regional-projects>).
- EOSC Governance and Sustainability Workshop (<https://ni4os.eu/2020/07/12/eosc-governance-and-sustainability-workshop/>).
- Synergies between Horizon and European structural and investment funds in EOSC Partnership (<https://ni4os.eu/2020/07/16/webinar-synergies-between-horizon-and-european-structural-and-investment-funds-in-eosc-partnership/>).
- NI4OS-Europe's participation in the EOSC Symposium 2020(<https://ni4os.eu/2020/10/22/ni4os-europes-participation-in-the-eosc-symposium-2020/>).
- FAIR Assessment and certification of digital objects and data repositories (<https://www.fairsfair.eu/news/fair-assessment-and-certification-eosc-region-report-available>).
- NI4OS-Europe participation at ESOF2020 dedicated session "[Advancing R&I ecosystems in the Western Balkans with regard to their ERA integration](#)".

In this we exploited optimally the available experts to enhance the quality of the events and achieve better technical and policy cohesion.

The project collaborated in joint effort of the fight against COVID-19 with fast access channels and information collected in the COVID-19 Wiki [11]. At the beginning of April 2020, we took part in the European Commission's social media campaign on COVID-19 contribution to raise awareness on the necessity of open science research workflows and the use of FAIR infrastructures within these burdensome times of the pandemic.

3. Marketing activities and results

NI4OS-Europe team is carrying out a set of activities aimed towards the fulfilment of the dissemination tasks described in section 2 “Dissemination activities” based on the core components of the project communication infrastructure. This chapter presents the project marketing activities which are complementary actions to the existing dissemination activities and bring them to the next level of proactive marketing, making the services offered by NI4OS-Europe more attractive to the end-users (as research communities, long tail of science, institutions, publishers) and to the data/service providers (infrastructures, data stewards, standards bodies). Where it was deemed advantageous, specific marketing actions were undertaken.

Since the target scope of the marketing activities consists of several target groups, the marketing activities were directed towards achieving several complementary goals, specifically designed to address the corresponding target groups. We consider the following main target groups, although some other groups were also addressed:

- Researchers (communities, organizations, long tail of science).
- Data/service providers.
- Research funders, policy makers and general audience (incl. public and business organizations).

First, we summarize the marketing activities and actions that were closely aligned with the corresponding dissemination or training activities.

- Many of the partners organized national dissemination events, supported by the NI4OS-Europe project – 8 events held up to M18, another 7 events will be held up to M21 (first half of the project after the extension). During these events, certain marketing activities were performed as there was good attendance by all the target groups described above.
- Presentations about the NI4OS-Europe project in general or some specific aspects of it were given in many scientific or technical conferences, workshops and meetings. In some of them the attendance included, apart from researchers, also policymakers. These presentations were used as a starting point to drive the discussions and address the most interested individuals or groups. In this way the point of view of the project’s participants found its way in national policy documents with relation to Open Science and EOSC. Establishing improved working relationships and channels of communication with other nationally recognized stakeholders/bodies was instrumental in marketing specific services and technical developments at the national level.
- By analyzing the attendance and feedback received at the training events, organized by the project, partners were able to identify researchers and research groups as well as in some cases potential data/service providers and engage them in further discussions and consultations in order to market the opportunities related to EOSC as appropriate for these target groups.
- The dissemination of some technical achievements of the project in scientific conferences or at other types of events was also an opportunity to market them to some of the interested participants.
- Several partners had events related to Data Management, FAIR and Open Science. Some of these events were more policy oriented, while other were more technical,

sometimes in collaboration with the national RDA teams. These events were used to present the portfolio of services and tools available in the project to people with already established interests in either using EOSC services or provisioning services and data in EOSC. In many cases as a result of these meetings follow-up discussions ensued with more targeted marketing actions.

When the target individuals or groups were identified and good contacts have been established, further specific marketing actions were performed:

- As it was planned some of the partners leveraged their contacts with technical or administrative leaders in the respective national branches of leading international companies or with SMEs with interests in software development or service provisioning in order to engage in fruitful discussion and drive towards fruitful collaboration. In some cases such partnerships resulted in formal contracts or grants.
- After analyzing the survey results, when contact details of persons that identified themselves as current or potential providers of services or data in the Open Science space were available, emails and other forms of communication were used in order to attempt to schedule meetings and discussions with topics that were deemed most relevant.
- Efforts were made in all the open or closed discussions and meetings, where national strategies are under consideration, to present the technical advantages of NI4OS-Europe services and to single out interested user groups and present them with more targeted information about the project and how they can benefit from the ease of use and capacity that is the landmark of the NI4OS-Europe services.

In Table 2 we present a summary report on the implementation of marketing activities during the first 18 months of the project, as they are formulated in the marketing plan in [4]. The Table 2 takes into account the partners' reported contributions reported divided into target groups (see Tables 10, 11, and 12 into Appendix D). We note that the COVID-19 pandemic resulted in delaying to some extent the implementation of the planned activities. We have taken measures to speed up their implementation by the end of the project, hoping to mitigate the impact of the pandemic.

Activity	Main marketing results	Partners involved
1. Marketing during national dissemination and national capacity building training events	Raised awareness of project innovations and opportunities, contacts established. 8 national dissemination events with more than 320 participants and 14 national training (capacity building) events with more than 450 participants. Established contacts with key participants.	All partners
2. Promote the on-boarding procedure and the pre-production environment developed by NI4OS-Europe	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (IICT): 2 national research infrastructures including into Bulgarian Roadmap for RI-DiSSCo-BG, CLADA BG; 2 data providers – NACID and Bulgarian RDA Node. • (SRCE): 1 data provider - Croatian RDA Node. 	All partners

through online and F2F meetings with providers of new thematic services/repositories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (IPB): 1 business organisation – Selectium company; 1 research organisation – Astronomical Observatory Belgrade. <p>Established contacts and partnership. Delivered consulting to RIs and Data providers</p>	
3. Create a concise and effective brochure with all NI4OS-Europe services/repositories clearly listed and emphasizes on these that are on-boarding in EOSC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (ATHENA): LCT Licence clearance tool, link. 2 brochures about EOSC & FAIR available in all mother languages of the NI4OS-Europe area via the project training platform (AL, AM, BA, BG, GE, GR, HR, HU, MD, ME, MK, RO, RS, SI) link. 	GRNET, ATHENA, UD, Partners having services/repositories for on-boarding
4. Publish popular articles about NI4OS-Europe results in a magazine or journal related to OSC	<p>List of publication articles is available in Appendix B.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5 articles (OA) published. 4 publications in national newsletters. 	Partners lead WPs
5. Participation with NI4OS-Europe presentation in relevant European/national events	<p>List of presentations is available in Appendix C.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 60 presentations devoted to NI4OS-Europe activities and achievements were presented in relevant European and national conferences/workshops. 	All partners
6. Organisation of special sessions or workshops in conferences – local or EOSC-related events	<p>NI4OS-Europe project was organizer / co-organiser on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Workshop: Extending and consolidating the EOSC offering: the regional views 11 April 2019 EOSC-hub week 2019 Link Online EOSC Governance and Sustainability Workshop “NI4OS-Europe met the EOSC GB country delegates” link. Online workshop on Policy landscape across Europe, 20 May 2020, at the EOSC-hub week 2020. Webinar “Interoperability in EOSC: OpenAIRE Guidelines for repositories” joint activities performed for OpenAIRE and NI4OS-Europe 11 June 2020 	All partners, PMB approves
7. Promotion of the NI4OS-Europe recommendations at events focused at funders, policy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> During the 28 national conferences/workshops (see Appendix A, Table 7). 	All partners

makers, and stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • During the 22 international conferences/workshops (see Appendix A, Table 8). • (IICT): Meetings with policy makers from the Ministry of Education and Science (MES), as members of OSWG for preparation the National Plan for Open Science (NPOS), published in State Gazette (issue 6 of 21.01.2021). • (GRNET/ATHENA) – meetings with policy makers from Ministries of Development, Ministry of Digital Governance, meetings with relevant stakeholders from R&E environment. <p><u>Results</u>: The NI4OS-Europe viewpoints were taken into account during preparation of policy documents.</p>	
8. Organize targeted meetings with Business Units and R&D departments of research-intensive SMEs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (IICT): 1 business organisation – Vmware Bulgaria. • (IPB): 1 business organisation – Selectium company. <p>Result: Improved partnership / signed contracts for joint activities in OS.</p>	All partners

Table 2: Summary of marketing results

4. Innovative results

In the last 18 months NI4OS-Europe carried out many innovative developments which are evaluated and assessed with the final aim to provide EOSC stakeholders added value.

Innovation in NI4OS-Europe is considered in relation to the region the project is operating in and the need of the stakeholders it is addressing. The frame has been set already during the definition of the innovation objectives during the NI4OS-Europe planning stage.

For implementing this objective, collecting information and monitoring this activity we created an Innovation Register. It is important to mention that the collection of the information was not left only to the Innovation Manager, but all partners participated in the collection process. This is to have a single point of reference of all innovations generated by the project, providing a resource to aid in the implementation of innovative techniques. It facilitates thereby their reuse and promotion. It also demonstrates that the NI4OS-Europe innovations satisfy the needs of a variety of target audiences; researchers, policy makers and industry/business.

The methodology to identify the innovative results and monitor the innovation process within the project is comprised by following steps:

- Stage 1: Idea generation and refinement at this stage the collection of innovation potentials, derivation of ideas, evaluation and release of ideas supervene.
- Stage 2: Evaluation and selection at this stage we outline an extensive analysis and derivation of concepts for the solution, implementation and marketing. Criteria: how successful they tackle the needs of the regional stakeholders and the region as a whole.
- Stage 3: Proof of concept at this stage the systematic testing of ideas which enables NI4OS-Europe to create and refine its innovations. An idea is converted to a product through the process of experimentation.
- Stage 4: Implementation at this stage the business and sustainability aspects are considered.
- Stage 5: Monitoring at this stage the data collection during implementation eventuate. The collected data should be compared with required results. If needed decide what types of actions have to be done for improvement.

Here we present the key innovative results that are candidate for further exploitation.

NI4OS-Europe innovative results can be categorized as follows.

- a. Community building: this includes all activities that support the EOSC awareness and capacity in the region; contributes to policies.
 - **NOSCI**: NOSCI are envisaged as coalitions of national organisations that have prominent roles and interest in the EOSC. NOSCI are supported by relevant Ministries and should become the mandated organisations to EOSC Association. This will allow them to promote synergies at national level, and to optimise/articulate their participation to EOSC and beyond. They will provide a link between EU Member States and EOSC and facilitate EOSC governance highlighting local strengths and weaknesses. They provide expertise in OS and OSC and will translate EOSC directions to local policies and strategies.

- **Translation officers** are a network of people with assigned tasks of translating documents related to the open science such as FAIR and EOSC training material as well as Incentives for ORDM to the native languages.
 - **EOSC promoters:** are a network of people active in Open Science who act as ambassadors for Open Science, EOSC, and FAIR at a national level. The network allows stakeholders of EOSC to be informed.
 - **Training materials:** The FAIR and EOSC Training Material was created, which was translated into 14 languages. The training material allows the project to reach out to all possible stakeholders of EOSC.
 - **Checklists:** They propose modular solutions for the setup of NOSCIs, giving to national initiatives maximum flexibility, while making sure that all important for them aspects are addressed.
 - **Stakeholders Map:** All NI4OS-Europe partners contributed in the Landscaping activity through a survey, which resulted in the stakeholder map. This map is available on the NI4OS-Europe website and it shows all OS stakeholders in a given region. NI4OS-Europe OS map shows the existing Open Science stakeholders in South East Europe, which have been identified and clustered on the basis of their role in important Open Science functions, i.e. funding, creating, supporting, consuming and facilitating OS [Link1](#), [Link2](#).
- b. Service provision: all activities that support the onboarding of services and repositories to EOSC.
- **Pre-production environment:** Based on the accumulated knowledge and partnership within the region, the pre-production environment offers EOSC compatible service integration to the regional service providers, enabling them to upgrade and integrate their services with the support from within the region.
 - **On-boarding platform and methodology:** The on-boarding methodology setup by NI4OS-Europe oversees different aspects of resources and aims to produce unique metrics to assess particular resources' impact. Recently it was practically realized as a portal - on-boarding dashboard - that tracks the progress and quality of a resource on-boarding to the EOSC. Both methodology and dashboard are scalable and could easily track and include further EOSC development. Organized into independent building blocks, both are extendable and can include some project-specific aspects of on-boarding.
 - **COVID-19 platform:** NI4OS-Europe fast access channel against COVID-19 gives access to NI4OS-Europe's generic services, tools and software for the scientific communities that perform extensive research requiring compute-intensive applications. With the establishment of this innovation, we were able to aid researchers and the overall scientific community in the fight against the pandemic.
 - **Training portal:** The portal is designed in such a way that provides a friendly environment for navigation throughout training material is available. It also incorporates the BigBlueButton, a specialized open-source plug-in, which enables partners hosting training events and

webinars. The portal is developed and administered by highly skilled researchers.

- c. FAIR and ORDM tools: these are the tools NI4OS-Europe is developing for supporting ORDM and FAIR in EOSC
- **LCT:** The [LCT-License Clearance Tool](#) (LCT) provides the environment for establishing the proper open-source licence required for the creation of a new (or synthetic) dataset, media, software etc. or for the re-use of existing unlicensed content. With this innovation the project was able to reach out to researchers, academic community regarding the topic of research data, software, and content in general.
 - **RoLeCT-** [EOSC RoP Legal & Ethics Compliance tool](#) was created which provides an aggregated guided assessment for EOSC Rules of Participations (RoP) focusing on legal and ethical aspects of compliance. This innovation allowed NI4OS-Europe project to reach out to service providers, researchers and research organizations.
 - **RePol:** is a tool to provide trustworthy repositories transparent policies, informing users about the roles, responsibilities, rights and procedures aimed at ensuring that their deposited data are preserved and disseminated in line with the FAIR principles. Having a repository policy is required for the on-boarding of scientific repositories and data into NI4OS-Europe and EOSC. RePol is to generate policies for repositories but it can be used to generate any other type of document, due to the versatile nature of its configurable forms and FreeMarker templates.

The innovative results identified here are further analysed with regards their sustainability potential in the next section. We have enhanced the innovation in existing solutions, but we also have developed new innovative services. Such as the EOSC promoters, who can have a disruptive role supporting the EOSC breakthrough in the region. There are also ideas on the list that were developed uniquely by NI4OS-Europe partners, e.g. the stakeholder map, or the LCT. Also, there were innovations implemented according to Open Science standards.

Project partners are devoted to promoting these innovations in their country therefore boosting the impact of NI4OS-Europe's overall project goals. The innovation activity results are aligned with the project's strategy, (1) to spread and train the EOSC and FAIR principles (awareness raising), (2) to support the development and inclusion of the national data related services and initiatives (on-boarding), and (3) to provide technical and policy support in the on-boarding processes (policy making).

Paying greater attention to the social dimensions of our outputs involving and engaging with a wider range of external and internal stakeholders (Table 6) whom the potential beneficiaries are of our results that were identified for exploitation and considered for sustainability. Preliminary evaluation was conducted through SWOT analysis for each innovative result in the following chapter.

The innovation register (see Figure 26) is available in project internal collaboration space, so that it is available to all partners and updated every time this is needed.

Objectives	Activities/Innovation/Service	Activities/Innovation/Service	Activities/Innovation/Service	Activities/Innovation/Service	Activities/Innovation/Service	Activities/Innovation/Service	Activities/Innovation/Service
Describe what is the goal of an innovation	Describe benefit for user	How the innovation contributes to the strategic goals of ECDC	What marketing actions are required	Describe how the intellectual property will be protected	List of collaborators	Describe actions for further development	Describe the business model/sustainability plan
The tool aims to mainstream concepts certification standards, tools and methodologies for open research data management and certification schemes for data repositories, aligning with activities and results of NI4OS-EC. It targets both data-intensive RSM (through cloud compute) and the service and handling of the long tail of science with the aim of establishing consolidated models of RSM activities in the research ecosystem. The tool aims at integrating a set of model procedures including: Model procedures for Copyright acquisition, management and dissemination public; Model Copyright clearance process, dissemination and tools; Model Data Protection (GDPR) compliance, processes, consent forms and data sharing agreements; Decision support trees for data protection policies.	Supports researchers to publish in FAIR/Open modes. Clearance not bound to the user that initiated the procedure, as it can be started and finished by different users. Clearance metadata will be an open source resource. Provide equivalence, interoperability and compatibility between licenses if used in combination, particularly for derivative works. Clearance attempts may be saved and assessed at a later time.	This is a certification tool for supporting transparency of repositories and ensuring their FAIRness in a standardized and interoperable fashion, with the objective to support the onboarding of repositories to ECDC.	Blog posts, Social Media posts, will be presented at appropriate webinars, conferences and workshops. It could be marketed as a Software as a Service to potential user communities outside of the project.	The software will be released under an open source license	The software is developed entirely by ITHENA EC. Feedback is requested from users within the NI4OS Europe consortium and researchers outside the project scope, as well related legal advisors.	The tool is currently in active development. Main objectives for future releases will be: Add a second workflow for clearance (from doctoral license to content). Add points of human interaction within the process (legal advisor). Add weighted, partial and full progress.	The application is still evolving such is early for a proper business model. The intention at the moment is to provide a basic free version for most common licenses with a pricing model for more advanced usage including business interactions with proper legal advisors for complex licensing schemes.
The network of people aims to promote and engage communities at a national level in all aspects of Open Science and the adoption and success of ECDC principles and vision.	Support all relevant stakeholders to understand, adopt and implement Open Science aspects and be part of the wider ECDC ecosystem.	Engagement of stakeholders is essential for the implementation of the ECDC vision. Awareness and participation are crucial for the success of ECDC. The ECDC promoters network is working towards ECDC and FAIR updates in communications.	Organize events/webinars. Organize or participate in relevant OS meetings of all levels, social media posts, webinars. Dissemination of training and other material.		NI4OS Europe consortium	Providing continuous training, material, feedback and knowledge will ensure a continuous process of knowledge transmission.	Building a "critical friends" network will providing the necessary tools and training will ensure a critical human infrastructure of knowledgeable resource and contact points for the future of ECDC.
The provision and dissemination of the produced material in 14 languages is an important mean to spread the mission and vision of ECDC and all aspects of Open Science.	Support all relevant stakeholders to understand, adopt and implement Open Science aspects and be part of the wider ECDC ecosystem.	Engagement of stakeholders is essential for the implementation of the ECDC vision. Awareness and participation are crucial for the success of ECDC. The material is essential to build the better understanding of ECDC and FAIR.	Disseminate and distribute whenever possible (national OS webinars, blogs, social media, meeting, events etc.)	Open license	Translations were made by NI4OS Europe translators.	Potential updates of the training material upon developments.	NI4 follow the sustainability plan of the project.
Operations	The onboarding methodology main objective is to identify resources that have an added value for the community and users and their address needs of a potentially large customer base. The dashboard aims to represent the identifier process visually and to allow tracking of the onboarding activities.	The onboarding methodology identifies resources with the highest relevance and impact to the ECDC users.	Identifies resources an automatically expand via the ECDC catalog.	We regularly present the onboarding methodology and dashboard to the ECDC community. We understand this as our contribution towards creating a unique ECDC onboarding methodology and associated tools. Therefore, our marketing activities are focused on the ECDC community.	At the moment, we don't see that our development may lead to the intellectual property which could be exploited commercially.	Methodology and dashboard are developed through the collaboration within the NI4OS Europe consortium. Both methodology and dashboard are presented to representatives of ECDC related projects, and further development will be based on feedback we receive from those stakeholders.	The methodology will be expanded with the additional aspects while the dashboard is in the early development stage and many features are still missing. Onboarding methodology and dashboard is our contribution to the ECDC, so the sustainability of those closely depend on the ECDC.

Figure 26: Innovation register

5. Sustainability plan updates

In the sustainability plan we have reexamined the main operational principles of the project in order to find the solutions for sustainable, long-term impact of our results. The project sustainability planning follows a 5-step process covering the whole duration of the project life cycle shown on Figure 27.

Figure 27: NI4OS-Europe sustainability process

The project is currently in phase 4 of the sustainability plan process, confirming commitments from interested partners to contribute to EOSC development processes. Having completed the previous three phases of the process, a solid ground has been created to build and expand contributions to EOSC. The activities that took place in each phase for the first three phases are described in Table 3. In the following sections we present the key results of the completed phases, namely a preliminary list of key project outputs with sustainability potential, individual SWOT analyses for the aforementioned outputs, beneficiaries' categorization and an overall SWOT analyses for the project. The section closes with an outlook to the next steps of phase 4.

Sustainability process phase	Activities
SP01: Setup and planning for development	<p>To identify and determine project results that could be further exploited and sustained and plan development the following actions were completed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> monitored ongoing activities to determine which ones could be exploited. identified collaborations related to sustainability platforms. identified key project results that could be further exploited.
SP02: Confirmed key results that will be explored	<p>On the grounds of D2.1 [14] – Stakeholder map, inventory and policy matrix landscaping study and the insights gained on the status of OSC initiatives, infrastructures, services, policies, stakeholders, and topics in partner countries, activities were initiated in the following areas:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • networking activities (policy support, training, and marketing) • service-oriented activities focusing on on-boarding services and service maintenance (on-boarding platform, pre-production environment). • FAIR, ORDM and EOSC-supporting tools development activities focusing on data standards, processes, certification and IPR (LCT - License Clearance Tool, RoLECT - EOSC RoP Legal & Ethics Compliance Tool, RePol Registry Policy Generator).
SP03: Confirmed target groups, beneficiaries	<p>As some key-tasks from phase 2 were completed, phase 3 activities were initiated including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trainings that were conducted and outreach programs that were organized to approach stakeholders. • Services on-boarding platform was tested, and operational practices were standardized. (First services have already been on-boarded) • marketing for innovation developments was defined and marketing activities started (marketing material, newsletters, blog articles, posters) <p>COVID-19 affected planned national dissemination events in this phase.</p>

Table 3: Sustainability process phases SP1 – SP3 and related activities

5.1. Project outputs with sustainability potential

Sustainability in NI4OS-Europe follows a dual path:

- a. for the innovative project outcomes, as they have been defined in previous section, sustainability pathways must be developed and
- b. the existence of project outcomes that address “sustainability by design”, such as the National Open Science Cloud Initiatives must be underpinned.

In phase 2 of the sustainability plan process, the project team has defined for which innovative project outputs sustainability actions must be undertaken. Major criteria have been their impact potential to the Southeast Europe region and their contribution potential to EOSC overall. This list may need to be revised and reformed during the project lifetime and it will be certainly finalized before the end of the project.

For better organizing work in the current sustainability phase of the project, this activity is following the clustering of NI4OS-Europe outcomes performed as part of the innovation activities of the project, as these two activities are obviously interwoven. The three main categories, as already indicated in the previous section and in the table above, follow at large the three key objectives of the project.

5.2. Evaluation of the project outputs with sustainability potential

After identifying the research outputs that have a sustainability potential for our region, a preliminary evaluation was conducted through SWOT analysis for each product, as shown in Table 4. This analysis will offer the team the leverage to focus on selected opportunities and addressable weaknesses of the identified research outputs.

Research output/ Activity	Strength	Weakness	Opportunities	Threats
OS Stakeholder map	The map has an easy-to-use interactive format helping the user to access the information effortlessly. It supports zoom functionality and filtering per country and stakeholder group which enable users to find the precise locations of stakeholders. Additionally, it supports easy access to information by supporting native languages of the 15 partner countries.	It supports only native languages. The map could be extended and support English too.	Organising national dissemination events and trainings is an opportunity for showcasing the map to national stakeholders, the main target group of the tool.	Political and economic changes in partner countries in the distant future may affect the operation of native stakeholders, leading to merge or closure of their organisations.
D2.2 Checklists	They propose modular solutions for the setup of NOSCIs, giving to national initiatives maximum flexibility, while making sure that all important for them aspects are addressed.	The checklists could be transferred into an online version offering greater usability.	The checklists were made known to partners during the workshop " Tools and examples for building NOSCIs and connecting them to EOSC ". Strong links to EOSC TFs and WGs, CPCB, and national efforts make D2.2 results visible at national, regional and international level.	A change of the EOSC governance schema affecting the operation of NOSCIs may affect the use of the D2.2 checklists.
NOSCIs	NOSCIs are envisaged as coalitions of national organisations that have prominent roles and interest in the EOSC. NOSCIs are	The coalition of organisations forming a NOSCI requires, in most cases, a lot of effort to make the first steps and will remain fragile until at least	Current status of EOSC Association provides a major window of opportunity for NOSCIs. Formed NOSCIs with	Time and proper timing of associated actions is considered essential for NOSCIs. NOSCIs should be established early enough to be

	<p>supported by relevant Ministries and should become the mandated organisations to EOSC Association. This will allow them to promote synergies at national level, and to optimise/articulate their participation to EOSC and beyond. They will provide a link between EU Member States and EOSC and facilitate EOSC governance highlighting local strengths and weaknesses. They provide expertise in OS and OSC and will translate EOSC directions to local policies and strategies.</p>	<p>an MoU has been signed among the members. This may be even more prominent for cases where government support is minimal or non-existent, especially after discussions for coalition have progressed to a maturity level. Effort is required to produce a lot of material that could be proposed to government officials to support the NOSCI's case.</p>	<p>official national support will have a strong saying in EOSC governance, steering decision making according to national strengths and weaknesses. Will become the mandated organisations to EOSC thus forming a stable link of bi-directional communication between EOSC and EU Member States. Will progressively ensure a significant percentage of EU OSC funding for national infrastructures and services. NOSCI's have the opportunity to fast forward OSC adoption to EU Member States mitigating risks and closing gaps between EOSC and local state of things fine tuning actions according to local pace and needs.</p>	<p>able to play a prominent role in both EOSC governance and national OSC strategy. Political uncertainty is a major threat for the formation and establishment of a NOSCI. Lack of official support will also result in a fragile NOSCI coalition that will have limited power in EOSC governance. Comparably a coalition that does not include all appropriate and relevant members of a national OS community will may seem insufficient for national representation.</p>
License Clearance Tool (LCT)	<p>An intuitive tool for content license clearance. It is particularly strong for derivative work that combines existing works. Provides license clearance through two guided workflows: resource-driven and license-driven. It is suitable for non-lawyers and the clearance is not bound</p>	<p>Requires further development, currently at stable version v3.0. New features and improvements are continuously being added. Pending release v4.0 will include the license-driven workflow and other enhancements. It has not been widely tested from the researchers' community, so</p>	<p>The specific demonstrator is innovative and answers the increased demand for providing technical solutions to address legal aspects in FAIR and ORDM. From the evaluations conducted, there are many researchers who find the tool interesting and potentially helpful, willing</p>	<p>Researchers may not be convinced of the product value at the moment, because use of the product is imposed and comes along the adoption of OS, OA and FAIR principles. User acceptance momentum may be lost in the meantime. Competitive product may emerge as FAIR and ORDM become widely accepted. A</p>

	<p>to the person who manages the data or has carried out the clearance procedure but to the work. May potentially include clearance for crowdsourced content. Development is in line with other related developments and collected/produced clearance metadata could be in a standardised machine-readable form and be provided under a permissive license. Usage takes into account both an automated free-tier and a cost-based human interaction model.</p>	<p>user feedback and acceptance are limited at the time being.</p>	<p>to contribute into testing. Training workshops and meetings with target users are required so as to train them how to use the application and gain user feedback and user acceptance insights.</p>	<p>face-to-face product launch/presentation is difficult due to COVID-19 restrictions, thus reducing impact making dissemination activities.</p>
<p>EOSC RoP Legal & Ethics Compliance</p>	<p>Aligned with the EOSC governance, this tool allows for IPR, ethics and data protection compliance both at the policy and legal level. The tool streamlines the assessment for EOSC RoP focusing on the demanding legal and ethical aspects compliance. Provides an aggregated guided assessment for EOSC RoP integrating model procedures for Copyright acquisition, management, dissemination policies and Data Protection (GDPR compliant) processes. Legal and ethics are two important</p>	<p>Currently at proof-of-concept stage. Pending stable release v1.0 will provide all basic functionality and coming releases will built on that. User feedback and acceptance is limited at the time being. Documentation of tool is a challenge due to the demanding fields addressed. The guided flow is very demanding regarding the questions stated and the decision paths followed, due to the context and specialised fields that must be presented in an intuitive way.</p>	<p>This can be considered an innovative tool answering the increased demand for providing technical solutions to address the needs for researchers to publish in FAIR/open modes. Targets service providers, researchers and research organisations in their increasing needs to interact with EOSC with services/datasets. RoLECT provides a specialised service for a need that has not been covered yet by other relevant tools, due to the nature and the difficulties associated with</p>	<p>The tool deals with a specialised yet essential aspect of EOSC RoP that may require specialised/trained staff to use it, if the wide audience finds it difficult to comprehend and interact with it. Will require test cases to be demonstrated that would happen in a still evolving EOSC RoP environment. A face-to-face product launch/presentation is difficult due to COVID-19 restrictions, thus reducing impact making dissemination activities.</p>

	aspects in the RoP that require particular focus due to their nature and the difficulties associated (specialised knowledge, experience, etc.) and as such, they have not yet been addressed adequately from other FAIR-related tools. Will allow users to follow varying paths to compliance with EOSC's RoP.		legal and ethics aspects in the RoP.	
Pre-production environment	Based on the accumulated knowledge and partnership within the region, the pre-production environment offers EOSC compatible service integration to the regional service providers, enabling them to upgrade and integrate their services with the support from within the region.	Lack of redundancy might affect the system's performance.	It is an environment that enables the partners to implement all the EOSC integration and on-boarding procedures with regional support for their services, that can then be automatically on-boarded to EOSC	The end of the NI4OS-Europe project will affect the seamless operation of the Pre-production environment.
Training portal	The portal is designed in such a way that provides a friendly environment for navigation throughout training material is available. It also incorporates the BigBlueButton, a specialized open-source plug-in, which enables partners hosting training events and	Like all technology tools and platforms, in case of failure of server, access to the portal is lost.	The portal can be enriched by training material covering all different aspects supported by NI4OS-Europe. Additionally, it can be used for the further uptake of topics related to EOSC and FAIR such as ORDM by anyone.	The end of the NI4OS-Europe project will affect the renewal of the training material in the portal.

	webinars. The portal is developed and administered by highly skilled researchers.			
EOSC promoters	EOSC promoters spread the word for EOSC and FAIR principles throughout different groups of actors related to the topic. By definition, they are informed for the latest developments of EOSC. They also familiarize stakeholders with the goals and activities of NI4OS-Europe such as the establishment of NOSCI.	An EOSC promoter is just one person with, sometimes, a very limited availability to represent the project in all events in which EOSC could play an important role.		Keeping EOSC promoters informed for the latest developments of EOSC is a challenge. Hence, after the end of the event it might be hard to manage the team in order to keep promoting EOSC.
Fast Access Channel against COVID-19	It provides an easy access to computational resources, thematic services and repositories for researchers who want to carry out cutting edge research against COVID-19. The access can be given extremely fast without the need of writing long proposals. The engaged researchers and machine administrators work closely for an efficient support of projects running within this initiative.	So far, the Fast Access Channel provides access to a few thematic services powered by two research groups participating in the action. Thus, there is the need for further advertisement to the scientific communities of countries participating in NI4OS-Europe.	It provides ground for establishment of collaborations between NI4OS-Europe and scientific teams in Life Sciences.	There is a low-risk threat of lack of computational resources to be provided to scientists applying for support from the NI4OS-Europe Fast Access Channel against COVID-19.
On-boarding methodology	Both methodology and dashboard are scalable and could easily tack and include	Since the EOSC is a dynamic environment, a permanent effort is required to monitor	At this development stage of the EOSC, the onboarding methodology	Once the EOSC portal becomes mature enough, the dashboard

and dashboard	further EOSC development. Organized into independent building blocks, both are extendable and can include some project-specific aspects of onboarding.	this development and incorporate new aspects into methodology and dashboard.	and dashboard could be used as the EOSC profiles specification testing environment.	might reach the end of its lifecycle.
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Table 4: SWOT analysis per project output

Target groups

Having completed phase 3 of the sustainability plan process, target groups have been identified mainly in Research and Education and Policy-making areas. Project dissemination activities will target stakeholders as in Table 5.

Area	Target groups
Research and education	Researchers, Academics, Educators. These are researchers, academics, and librarians in mainly European Universities and research organisations. The group includes also educators involved in OS fields.
Policymaking and funding	Local, national and EU policy makers & funders, Project Managers, private funders. These are decision-makers in government and governmental funding agencies who design tenders and fund programmes related to OS and R&I, in Europe and beyond, project managers from OS related programmes and companies that fund independent research projects.

Table 5: NI4OS-Europe target groups and beneficiaries

The above confirmed target groups were associated with project results that were identified for exploitation and considered for sustainability, based on what would potentially be beneficial for them. Table 6 shows this categorization.

Project results	Researchers	Academics & librarians	Educators	Policy-makers	Funders
OS Stakeholder map	X			X	X
D2.2 Checklists	X	X			
NOSCIs	X	X	X	X	X
License Clearance Tool (LCT)	X	X	X		
EOSC RoP Legal & Ethics Compliance	X	X	X		
Training & training portal	X	X		X	
EOSC promoters	X	X		X	X
Services onboarding platform	X	X	X	X	

Table 6: NI4OS-Europe target groups and beneficiaries

In the final sustainability report and the forthcoming business analysis, these associations between target groups and project results will be further examined and expanded.

Next steps: phase 4

Next steps in phase 4 involve consortium partners committed to innovations and exploitation of findings to expand on these activities, raising awareness, on-boarding more services and pushing policy making in the OSC area. Activities will continue in national levels and the collaboration and relationships established with EOSC channels and networks will be sustained, specifically these will include:

- Establishing NOSCI in all NI4OS-Europe partner countries and promoting policies and frameworks for OSC strategic plans.
- Training on NOSCI with webinars, blogposts, and face-to-face events if possible.
- Establishing in each NOSCI strong partner links in every NI4OS-Europe partner country to promote and further exploit project results.
- Analyzing potential business models while maintaining collaboration with other INFRAEOSC-5b projects.
- Exploiting the collaborative international network of OpenAIRE.
- Onboarding more services to NI4OS-Europe catalogue.
- Products development: Improving WP4 tools and bringing them to a development stage “close to the market”. In parallel consider business models for those, to allow for their exploitation and sustainability after the closing of the project.

6. Conclusion

The reported dissemination, marketing and innovation activities during the first 18 months were based on the initial dissemination and marketing plans presented in the project deliverable D7.2. These plans were further updated and adapted according to the current situation – the COVID-19 pandemic with all restrictions connected to it, and to new project needs. Dissemination events were organised online using the project platform. Complimentary dissemination events were included in the marketing plan, most of them took place online. 8 national dissemination events were organized during the reporting period with more than 320 participants; another 7 events are planned for the next 3 months. The remaining planned regional and national dissemination events will be organized during the remaining time of the project.

Promotional package has been produced and distributed at a number of events. General project presentation is frequently used and it is updated regularly to include the new developments and achievements of the project. The web presence consists of a NI4OS-Europe official web site, NI4OS-Europe event portal, NI4OS-Europe training portal, NI4OS-Europe Wiki, and NI4OS-Europe section vs COVID-19. The social media accounts are actively used to make project achievements and intensive work visible to the society as a whole. Various types of dissemination materials were produced for use by the project (5 posters, 2 project brochures, 2 physical and 4 web banners, etc). Social media campaigns have been carried out, press releases issued, newsletters circulated and 60 presentations and 9 publications delivered.

Innovation and marketing strategies have been developed and activities performed according to the plan. The project innovation register has been designed, regularly monitored and the innovative developments actively disseminated and marketed. In the sustainability plan the main operational principles of the project have been re-examined in order to find the solutions for sustainable, long-term impact of our results.

The dissemination and marketing activities will intensify online after the initial adaptation period to the new COVID-19 situation, and will restart in person when circumstances allow.

Appendix A List of events with NI4OS-Europe participation

Participation at National Conferences/Workshops

№	Event title/ Conference/ Workshop	Date/ Place	NI4OS-Europe representation (talks, materials, booth, discussions, etc.)	Audience	Link of the event
1	9th professional meeting of Slovenian purchasing consortia of international scientific literature Workshop "Focus on Open Science"	8 Nov 2019, University of Ljubljana, Slovenia	UMUKM gave a presentation, landscape survey invitation handout	policymakers, service providers, librarians, publishers	Link1 , Link2
2	Open Science 2019: Open Research Data in Slovenia and workshops for researchers	14 th -15 th Nov, 2019, University of Maribor Library	UMUKM and ARNES: presentations, discussions, landscape survey invitation handout	80 attendees: Policymakers, service providers, librarians, researchers, students, publishers	Link
3	Network of Knowledge 2019	Arnes, 4 th December 2019	ARNES: Presentation	Policymakers, IT professionals, service providers, teachers, librarians, general public	Link
4	Round Table "Problems of Open Science in the Republic of Moldova", co-organized by presented other international projects that were recently started Moldova.	12 Dec 2019, Chisinau Moldova	RENAM, presentation, Dr. Peter Bogatencov	45 attendees: librarians, researchers, students	Link
5	Workshop "E-Infrastructure of scientific data to support research and increase the socio-economic impact of science in the Republic of Moldova	16 Dec 2019, Information Society Development Institute, Chisinau Moldova	RENAM: discussions Mrs. Natalia Cheradi attended	service providers, researchers	Link
6	RDA Node Slovenia Conference: Scientific Journals and Research Data	Faculty of Social Sciences at the University of Ljubljana,	UMUKM: Presentation, discussion	Publishers, librarians, service providers, researchers	Link1 , Link2

		28 th Jan, 2020			
7	HRDA meetup series (9 events)	March 4 th – November 2020	On 14 th May 2020 Janos Mohacsi (KIFU) presented EOSC; on 29 th June 2020 Judit Fazekas-Paragh (DE) presented NI4OS-Europe	Researchers, research support staff, funders	Link , Link
8	Meeting of the Council of LAM (Library Association of the Republic of Moldova)	7 April, 2020, Chisinau, Moldova	RENAM: Information on the Open Science Landscape Survey results and other NI4OS-Europe project activities was presented	Publishers, librarians, repository providers	Link
9	Open Research Data and Scientific Excellence: public discussion organized by the Central Technical Library at the University of Ljubljana	Online, 21 st April 2020	UMUKM: Discussion	Policymakers, service providers, researchers, students, publishers, librarians	Link
10	Interoperability in EOSC: OpenAIRE Guidelines for repositories” webinar	Online, 17 June 2020	UCY Discussions	Publishers, librarians, service providers, researchers	Link
11	RDA Node Slovenia Conference: Research Data and European Open Science Cloud Conference – Session: European Open Science Cloud	Online, 18 June 2020	UMUKM: presentation, EOSC session moderating, round table discussion	Policymakers, service providers, researchers, students, publishers, librarians	Link1 , Link2
12	EOSC Governance and Sustainability Workspop:	Online, 08 July 2020	All NI4OS-Europe partners	NI4OS-Europe partners met the EOSC GB country	Link
13	Meeting on Researcher Network Data Archive for Social Sciences in Bosnia and Herzegovina	online 14 July 2020	UNIBL	Service providers, researchers	Link
14	Workshop on Data Management organized by RDA Bulgarian Node	Online, 24 July, 2020	IICT participated with NI4OS-Europe presentation	35 attendees: Services and Data providers, stakeholders and research funders and policy makers	Link
15	Networkshop 2020 Hungary	September 4-6 2020	DE, KIFU (presentations: Judit Fazekas-Paragh, Edit Görögh, Adam Szaldobagyi, Gyöngyi Karácsony – DE; János Mohácsi, Tamás Máray – KIFU)	ICT researchers, library and information scientists, developers (300 attendees)	Link
16	PUBMET2020: The 7th Conference on Scholarly Communication and Publishing in the Context of Open Science	Online, 16-18 Sept 2020	SRCE: presentation	46 attendees: Policymakers, service providers, researchers,	Link

				students, publishers, librarians	
17	PubMet 2020 Conference: Slovenian Research Infrastructure and Open Science	Online, 18 Sept, 2020	UMUKM: Presentation, discussion	Policymakers, service providers, researchers, students, publishers, librarians	Link1 , Link2
18	The 11-th National Information Day: "Open Science, Open Data, Open Access, Bulgarian OSC	Online, 25 Sept, 2020	IICT participated with NI4OS-europe presentation	40 attendees Researchers, policymakers, service providers, publishers, librarians	Link
19	Open Science and Intellectual Property Rights	25 Sept, 2020 the University of Banja Luka (EURAXESS)	UNIBL	Service providers, researchers	Link
20	FAIR Competences for Higher Education Design Workshop.	Online, 8-9 Oct, 2020	UNIBL participated	Researchers communities, students	Link
21	Open Science 2020 Conference: Open Science in Slovenia and the European Open Science Cloud: infrastructural aspects.	Online, 21 Oct 2020	UMUKM: Presentation, discussion	Policymakers, service providers, researchers, students, publishers, librarians	Link1 , Link2
22	The National Open Science Days in Serbia	Online 5-6 Nov 2020	UoB team organized and participated. IPB team participated. Presentations, discussion	Researchers, librarian, policy-makers, research support staff	Link
23	Transferable Skills for Doctoral Students Course	Online, 17 th Nov 2020	UMUKM: Presentation, brochures	Students, researchers	Link
24	European Researchers' Night in the Republic of Moldova	Online, 27 Nov 2020	RENAM presentation	General public	Link
25	Biomedical Circle: Open Research Data in Medicine	Online, 10 th Dec 2020	UMUKM Presentation, discussion	Service providers, researchers, students, librarians	Link
26	Research Libraries, Researchers & the EOSC: Multidisciplinary Universities.	Online, 25 th Jan 2021	UCY Presentation, Discussions	Data providers, researchers, publishers, librarians	Link
27	Research Data Management Support in Libraries	Online, 27 th Jan 2021	UMUKM Presentation, brochures, discussion	Librarians, research support staff	Link

28	RDM meetup (11 meetups)	From 25 th November 2020 – February 5 th 2021	Ádám Száldobágyi (DE) presented 5 times on EOSC, FAIR, ORDM, Judit Fazekas-Paragh presented on Open Science (DE)	Researchers	Link
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Table 7: List of national conferences/workshopsParticipation at International Conferences/Workshops:

Nº	Event title/ Conference/ Workshop	Place/ Date	NI4OS-Europe representation (talks, materials, booth, discussions, etc.)	Audience	Link of the event
1	EOSC Symposium	26-28 Nov, 2019, Budapest, Hungary	UOB, SRCE, KIFÜ, DE: NI4OS-Europe presentations by Ivan Maric and Biljana Kosanović	Polymakers, service/ repository providers, researchers, funders, publishers, librarians	Link1 , Link2
2	International Conference "Research Infrastructures of the Future" (FUTURIS 2019)	10-11 Dec 2019, National Palace of Culture, Sofia, Bulgaria	IICT Brochures, Discussions	around 200 attendees: stakeholders, policymakers	Link
3	Meeting of the Commission expert group on National Points of Reference on Access to and Preservation of Scientific Information	21-22 Jan, 2020, Brussels	UNIBL represented by Dragana Radulovic. RBI represented by Jadranka Stojanovski	Polymakers, service/repository providers, researchers, funders,	Link
4	EOSC-hub week: workshop on Policy landscape across Europe	Online, 20 May 2020	NI4OS-Europe project was co-organiser All partners participation NI4OS-Europe presentation by Biljana Kosanovic Panel discussions	Representatives from EOSC-related initiatives and projects, Members of the EOSC Governance, repository managers	Link
5	EOSC-hub week Special Session: Innovation from the EOSC regional projects	Online 18-20 May, 2020	All NI4OS-Europe partners participation NI4OS-Europe presentation by Judit Eva Fazekas-Paragh (DE)	Service providers, research infrastructures, scientific communities, repository managers, universities, researchers	Link

6	The first open e-IRG Workshop webinars in 2020 under the Croatian EU Presidency	Online, 25-26 May, 2020	Project presentation by S. Filipovska (UKIM) Representatives from SCRE, IICT, RENAM, UEFISCDI, ICI, and GRENA participated.	Policymakers, service/repository providers, researchers, e-infrastructures providers	Link
7	Webinar: "Synergies between Horizon and European structural and investment funds in EOSC Partnership" organized by EOSC-Pilar project	Online, 20 July 2020	IICT, UEFISCDI, ICI participated	Policy-makers, funders, stakeholders	Link
8	ESOF2020 session "Advancing R&I ecosystems in the Western Balkans with regard to their ERA integration"	Online, 04 Sept, 2020	GRNET, Presentation Discussions	99 online views in real time	Link
9	Open Science related sessions of the European Research and Innovation Days	Online, 22-24 September 2020	KIFÜ participated	Stakeholders, Research communities,	Link
10	EOSC Governance Symposium	Online, 19-22 Oct, 2020	All NI4OS-Europe partners NI4OS-Europe presentation by Anastas Mishev (UKIM)	977 stakeholders from 52 countries	Link
11	EOSC association bylaws webinar	Online, 20 Oct, 2020	Dusan Vudragovic from IPB and (UNIBL) participated	Service/repository providers, researchers	Link
12	EGI Conference 2020	Online, 2-5 Nov, 2020	GRNET, IICT, GRENA, KIFU Presentation Discussions	Almost 200 attendees: Stakeholders Service/data providers	Link1 , Link2
13	Global OS Cloud workshop	Online, 3-4 Nov, 2020	GRNET, IICT, KIFU discussions	76 attendees Stakeholders Service/data providers	Link
14	EAHIL: Library Services in the Changing Data Culture	16 th November 2020	Presented by: Edit Görögh (DE)	Researchers, librarians, information scientists	Link
15	The EOSC bylaws consultation follow-up webinar	Online, 26 Nov, 2020	Dusan Vudragovic from IPB participated, KIFÜ	Service/repository providers, researchers	Link
16	The e-IRG Virtual Workshop under the German EU Presidency	Online, 1-2 Dec, 2020	SCRE, IICT Discussions UEFISCDI participated	Around 90 attendees: Stakeholders Member States delegates in e-IRG group	Link
17	EOSC GA	Online, December 2020	KIFÜ participated	Service providers, researchers	Link
18	GÉANT Infoshare on FAIR Principles and RDA	Online, 02 December, 2020	KIFÜ participated	Around 60 attendees	
19	EOSC Enhance webinar on EOSC Portal Improvements	Online, 03 December 2020	KIFÜ participated	Around 100 attendees	

20	LIBER – Scientific Knowledge Services (main topic: EOSC)	January 20 th 2021	Presented by: Judit Fazekas-Paragh (DE)	researchers, research librarians	Link
21	LIBER – Scientific Knowledge Services (main topic: EOSC)	January 18 th 2021	Presented by: Biljana Kosanovic, Milica Sevkusic	30 participants, researchers, research librarians	Link
22	Webinar “Aligning Research Data Management Across Europe – The next step”	Online, 27 Jan, 2021	IICT. UEFISCDI participated	Almost 300 attendees: Funders, Stakeholders Policy makers Research communities	Link1 Link2

Table 8: List of international conferences/workshops

Appendix B List of publications supported by the NI4OS-Europe project

Nº	Authors	Title	Publication	Link
1	(GRNET, ATENA, DE) Drago, F., Prnjat, O., Toli, E., Fazekas-Paragh, J., et all.	Position papers on EOSC - Insights from Regional Projects & Infrastructures	Zenodo, May 18, 2020, http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3831561 ,	link
2	(ICI) Vevera, A.V., Barbu,link D.C., Neagu, G., Ciuperca, E.	NI4OS-Europe project -support for the National Open Science Cloud Initiative	Romanian Journal of Information Technology and Automatic Control, 30(2), 2020, ISSN 1220-1758	Link
3	(UoBL) M. Savić, M. Ljubojević and S. Gajin	A Novel Approach to Client-Side Monitoring of Shared Infrastructures	IEEE Access, vol. 8, pp. 44175-44189, 2020, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2978172	Link
4	(UOB) Otašević, Vladimir, & Kosanović, Biljana	Application of Open-source Software in Data Visualization	PSSOH conference paper on open source software for data visualization, 26 Oct, Belgrade, Serbia: Zenodo.	Link1 , Link2
5	(RENAM) Nichita Degteariov, Petru Bogatencov, Nicolai Iliuha, Grigore Secieru	Upgrading Cloud Infrastructure for Research Activities Support	Proceedings of the Workshop on Intelligent Information Systems (WIIS2020), December 4-5, 2020, Chisinau, Republic of Moldova, pp. 69-74, ISBN 978-9975-68-415-6.	Link
6	(SRCE) Katarina Zailac, Kristina Posavec	Webinari o korištenju infrastrukture EGI i upravljanju istraživačkim podacima	SRCE Newsletter, No 80, p. 13	Link
7	(SRCE) Kristina Posavec, Draženko Celjak	Integracija hrvatskih podatkovnih repozitorija u EOSC / Integration of Croatian repositories into EOSC	SRCE Newsletter, No 81, p. 8	Link
8	(SRCE) Kristina Posavec	Koncept otvorene znanosti – koliko uistinu znamo? / Open Science – How much do we know?	SRCE Newsletter, No 81, p. 9	Link
9	(RBI) Bojan Macan	Mrkva i batina na NI4OS-Europe način /Carrot and stick in NI4OS-Europe way	SRCE Newsletter, No 81, p. 7	Link

Table 9: List of publications

Appendix C List of NI4OS-Europe presentations

1. (GRNET) O. Prnjat, "NI4OS-Europe" presentation, GEANT South East Europe NREN Directors Workshop, 4th September 2019, Athens.
2. (GRNET) O. Prnjat, participation in panel on "EOSC Readiness" during EPOS Implementation Phase Project final event in Madrid, 25-27 September 2019.
3. (GRNET) O. Prnjat, keynote speech "European Open Science Cloud: perspectives for the UbuntuNet region and beyond", UbuntuNetConnect 2019 conference, Antananarivo, 29 October – 1 November, 2019, Antananarivo.
4. (GRNET) O. Prnjat, keynote speech "Building National Initiatives for Open Science – NI4OS-Europe", ESOF2020 session "Advancing R&I ecosystems in the Western Balkans with regard to their ERA integration"
5. (BRFAA) Z. Cournia presented as Keynote speaker at the 1st EOSC Symposium in Budapest, Hungary on 26.11.2019 with title: "The added value of EOSC for research", ([Link](#)).
6. (ATHENA RC) Poster presentation, "NI4OS-Europe: Building National Initiatives for Open Science in Europe", OSFair2019, 16-18 September 2019, Porto, Portugal.
7. (ATHENA RC) E. Papadopoulou, "The journey to EOSC preparing at national level", OSFair2019, 16-18 September 2019, Porto, Portugal.
8. (ATHENA RC) E. Toli, presentation of NI4OS-Europe overview in Panel Discussion of FAIR Metrics parallel session, at the 1st EOSC Symposium in Budapest, Hungary on 26.11.2019.
9. (ATHENA RC) E. Toli, presentation of NI4OS-Europe scope, objectives and partnership, the candidate generic & thematic services for on-boarding to EOSC, as well as the short-term roadmap of the project in the "EOSC as a Federation" plenary session, at the 1st EOSC Symposium in Budapest, Hungary, 26-28.11.2019.
10. (CYI) A. Athenodorou presented NI4OS-Europe in the OpenAIRE workshop "Open Science: From theory to practice" in Cyprus, 24th of October 2019.
11. (UCY) V. Koukounidou, presented NI4OS-Europe in Open Access week event organized by Cyprus OpenAIRE NOAD on the 24th of October 2019. The title of the event was "Open Science: From theory to practice" Website program and pictures of the event: ([Link](#))
12. (IICT) A. Karaivanova presented the NI4OS-Europe project during the OPEN DAYS in IICT, 3-4 October 2019.
13. (IICT) A. Karaivanova presented the NI4OS-Europe project at the UNESCO conference Digital economy new challenges and the role of women", 15-16 October 2019, Technical University of Sofia.
14. (DE) J. Fazekas-Paragh Presented NI4OS-Europe in the HUNOR OS MeetUp, 17. October 2019, Budapest.
15. (UOB) B. Kosanovic, "NI4OS-Europe - National Initiatives for Open Science in Europe, Coming together to map the national landscape analysis on EOSC between 5 relevant projects, 11th October 2019, Conference-call ([Link](#)).
16. (UMUKM) D. Legat, "Slovenian initiative for a National Open Science Cloud: project NI4OS-Europe and national activities", Conference Focus on Open Science, 8 November 2019, ([Link](#)).
17. (UMUKM) D. Legat, "Open and FAIR data: plans within the NI4OS-Europe project", Conference Open Research Data in Slovenia, 14 November 2019, ([Link](#)).
18. (UMUKM) D. Legat, "New era of collaboration: presentation of the NI4OS-Europe project", Conference Open Research Data in Slovenia, 14 November 2019, ([Link](#)).
19. (UMUKM) D. Legat, "National initiatives for open science: examples of good practices", Conference Open Research Data in Slovenia, 14 November 2019, ([Link](#)).
20. (UMUKM) B. Klemenčič, "Open science: where are we? – NI4OS-Europe landscape survey presentation", Conference Open Research Data in Slovenia, 14 November 2019, ([Link](#)).
21. (UOB) Biljana Kosanović, NI4OS-Europe landscape survey, EOSC Symposium, Budapest, 27 November 2019.
22. (ARNES) Jan Jona Javoršek, Jožef Stefan Institute, Slovenian national supercomputing network and operation HPC RIVR, Conference Mreža znanja 2019, 4 December 2019 ([Link](#)).
23. (RENAM) Dr. Peter Bogatencov made presentation "NI4OS_Europe: European Open Science Cloud Initiative – Support of Open Science in the South Eastern Europe" devoted to NI4OS-Europe project in general, specific activities planned for Moldova, and perspective of formation of the National Open Science Initiative at the Round table "Problems of Open Science in the Republic of Moldova", which took place on December 12, 2019 in Chisinau, Moldova.

24. (UMUKM) D. Legat, "Overview of Global Practices", RDA Node Slovenia Conference: Scientific Journals and Research Data, 28 January 2020, ([Link](#)).
25. (UMUKM) D. Legat, "Overview of Global Practices", RDA Node Slovenia Conference: Scientific Journals and Research Data, 28 January 2020 ([Link](#)).
26. (UOB) Biljana Kosanović, NI4OS-Europe National Initiatives for Open Science in Europe, RCC meeting, Brussels, 21 January 2020 (in the Box).
27. (IPB) Dusan Vudragovic presented the EOSC Infrastructures and Services during the EOSC promoters' train-the-trainers event held on 16-17 March 2020. In this two-hour presentation, he covered the current EOSC development stage, described what kind of infrastructures and services the EOSC promoters should approach, gave details about the current on-boarding procedure, as well as links to the relevant training material that can be reused.
28. (IICT) E. Atanassov "NI4OS-Europe - National Initiatives for Open Science in Europe", online seminar presentation and virtual tour for students, Plovdiv University, Faculty of Mathematics and Informatics, 29.04.2020.
29. (IPB) Dusan Vudragovic presented the EOSC virtual research environment during the national capacity building event in Bosnia and Herzegovina held on 27 May 2020. In his talk, the following topics have been included: EOSC aims and regional perspective, EOSC-core, federated data, EOSC-Exchange, services within the NI4OS-Europe project, EOSC Working Groups and EB Task Forces, EOSC on-boarding and different aspects of resource description, cumulative levels of integration, and best practices for on-boarding.
30. (UOB) Biljana Kosanović, Milica Ševkušić, NI4OS-Europe National Initiatives for Open Science in Europe, EOSC-hub Week 2020, 20 May 2020, ([Link](#)).
31. (DE) Judit Eva Fazekas-Paragh, "The role of NI4OS-Europe in OS Innovation in South-East Europe", EOSC-hub week 2020: Online workshop on Innovation from the EOSC regional projects, 20 May 2020, [link](#).
32. (DE) Judit Eva Fazekas-Paragh, "HRDA Meetup: Hogyan támogatja a NI4OS-Europe projekt a nyílt tudományt Dél-Kelet Európában?", HRDA: for the Hungarian Research Data Alliance Community , June 29th 2020, [link](#).
33. (DE) Judit Eva Fazekas-Paragh, "Building an Open Scholarly Ecosystem in Europe", Networkshop, 2020. szeptember 2-4., Pécs, MS Teams Virtuális tér - NI4OS-Europe, [link](#).
34. (GRNET) Ognjen Prnjat presented "Building National Initiatives for Open Science - NI4OS-Europe" during virtual session Advancing R&I ecosystems in the Western Balkans with regard to their ERA integration at ESOF 2020 (4 September 2020, Virtual Room 3 – 12:00 – 13:30).
35. (UOB) Biljana Kosanović, Developments in Serbia, EOSC Governance and Sustainability Workshop, 8 July 2020.
36. (UMUKM) D. Legat, "Digital skills for the European Open Science Cloud (Digitalne veščine za Evropski oblak odprte znanosti)", Research Data and European Open Science Cloud Conference, 18 June, 2020, ([Link1](#)), ([Link2](#)).
37. (UMUKM) Legat, D. Digital skills for European Open Science Cloud (Digitalne veščine za Evropski oblak odprte znanosti), ([Link](#)), Research Data and European Open Science Cloud Conference, June 18, 2020 .
38. (IICT) T. Gurov "Possible joint activities of RDA BG Node with NI4OS-Europe project on a National Level", online Workshop on Data Management, ZOOM platform, 24th of July 2020 (in NI4OS-Europe box).
39. (UMUKM) D. Legat, "Slovenian research infrastructure and Open Science – new challenges, PubMet 2020 Conference, 18 September 2020. ([Link](#)).
40. (UMUKM) Legat, D. Slovenian Research Infrastructure and Open Science – New Challenges. PubMet 2020 Conference, September 18th 2020. ([Link](#)),
41. (IICT) Aneta Karaivanova, "NI4OS-Europe project", 11th National Information Day, 25 September 2020. ...
42. (UMUKM) D. Legat, "Open Science in Slovenia and the European Open Science Cloud: infrastructural aspects". Open Science 2020 Conference, 21 October 2020, ([Link1](#)), ([Link2](#)).
43. (UOB) Vladimir Otašević, Biljana Kosanović, Primena softvera otvorenog koda kod vizualizacije podataka, PSSOH Conference - Application of Free Software and Open Hardware, Belgrade, 24 October 2020, ([Link](#)).
44. (UOB) Milica Ševkušić, On the way to EOSC: NI4OS-Europe, Open Science Days, Belgrade, 6 November 2020, ([Link](#)).
45. (UOB) Biljana Kosanović, NI4OS-Europe and EOSC, Open Science Days, Belgrade, 6 November 2020, ([Link](#)).
46. (UOB) Branko Marović, Alati za otvorenu nauku – NI4OS-Europe katalog; demonstracija alata; NI4OS-Europe i COVID-19, Open Science Days, Belgrade, 6 November 2020, ([Link](#)).

47. (UOB) Vladimir Otašević, Vizualizacija otvorenih podataka, Open Science Days, Belgrade, 6 November 2020, ([Link](#)).
48. (UOB) Slavko Gajin, Primena računarstva u oblaku u naučno-istraživačkom radu, Open Science Days, Belgrade, 6 November 2020, ([Link](#)).
49. (UMUKM) D. Legat, B. Klemenčič, "Research Data Management", Transferable skills for doctoral students of the University of Maribor course, 17 November 2020, ([Link1](#)), ([Link2](#)).
50. (ARNES) The European Open Science Cloud, Peter Sterle (Ministry of Education, Science and Sport/EOSC GB). ([Link1](#)), ([Link2](#)).
51. (IPB) IPB's Dusan Vudragovic participated in the National Open Science Days in Serbia organized from 5-6 November 2020. During the NI4OS-Europe dedicated session, he presented the EOSC virtual research environment and relevant tools.
52. (IPB) Within the EOSC on-boarding task force, Dusan Vudragovic presented NI4OS-Europe on-boarding activities.
53. (UMUKM) D. Legat, "EOSC – The European Open Science Cloud", Conference Biomedical Circle: Open Research Data in Medicine, 10 December 2020, ([Link](#)).
54. (UOB) Biljana Kosanović, Pioniri otvorene nauke, Open Science Pioneers, Belgrade, 29 December 2020, ([Link](#)).
55. (UOB) Milica Ševkušić, EOSC Portal, Open Science Pioneers, Belgrade, 29 December 2020, ([Link](#)).
56. (UOB) Biljana Kosanović, Milica Ševkušić, What do Southern-Eastern Europe (SEE) librarians know about EOSC and FAIR data? Not enough, Research Libraries, Researchers & the EOSC: Southern European Landscape, 18 Jan 2021, [link](#).
57. (UMUKM) D. Legat, "Open:UM for research data: an example of training at the University of Maribor", RDA Node Slovenia Workshop Research Data Management Support in Libraries, 27 January 2021, ([Link1](#)), ([Link2](#)).
58. (SRCE) Ivan Marić, EOSC Symposium, Budapest, Hungary, 26 November 2019, ([Link](#)).
59. (SRCE) Ivan Marić, EOSC Governance and Sustainability Workshop, 8 July 2020, ([Link](#)).
60. (SRCE) Emir Imamagić, PUBMET2020: The 7th Conference on Scholarly Communication and Publishing in the Context of Open Science, 16 September 2020, ([Link](#)).

Appendix D List of partners' marketing activities to main target groups

Country/ partner	Implementing date	Description of action
All Partners	22/10/2019 – 04/12/2019	Survey – sending invitations to participate in the landscape survey of stakeholders (research communities, organisation and end-users).
	1/9/2019- 28/02/2021	Marketing NI4OS-Europe achievements during national capacity building training events and national dissemination events.
	September 2019-ongoing	Sharing information about NI4OS-Europe on-boarding generic and thematic services on social media and the local project webpages.
	September 2019-ongoing	Sharing information on our social media platforms regularly regarding EOSC infrastructure and NI4OS-Europe repositories services.
	April, July, November 2020	Dissemination of NI4OS-Europe newsletters, Issue N°1, 2, 3 among stakeholders (research communities, organisation and end-users).
EL/GRNET SA, ATHENA RC	16 Sept. 2019	The poster entitled " NI4OS-EUROPE: Building National Initiatives for Open Science in Europe " was presented at the OSFair2019 (16-18 Sept. 2019) displaying an overview of the project's mission and objectives, the core actions, the expected outcomes, and the target region.
	7 February 2020	Created a Zenodo community to deposit and disseminate projects deliverables and outputs.
	8 July 2020	Posting the blog article: "EOSC Governance and Sustainability: NI4OS-Europe meets the EOSC GB country delegates" on NI4OS-Europe website announcing the EOSC Governance and Sustainability Workshop, https://ni4os.eu/2020/07/12/eosc-governance-and-sustainability-workshop/ .
	2 November 2020	Posting the blog article: "LCT: a license clearance tool for research outputs re-use" on NI4OS-Europe site announcing the deployment of the LCT tool.
	9-12 November 2020	The License Clearance Tool (LCT) poster was presented online during the RDA 16th Plenary Meeting , (9-12 November 2020) and introduced LCT features, assets and the two workflows that it supports.
	30 November 2020	Posting the blog article: "The first year of NI4OS-Europe" on NI4OS-Europe site sharing the milestones of project's first year of operation.
	Sept 2019 – June 2020	Participating in the consultations of the Greek Open Science Working Group which resulted in the formulation of the National Plan for Open Science .
	February 2021	Producing D2.2 checklists: transforming content from D2.2 into easy-to-use tools (checklists) in a brochure format for establishing the NOSCI.
	November 2020 – ongoing	Populating the project wiki page with COVID-19 resources and information on the License Clearance Tool (LCT) and Registry Policy Generator (RePol) tool.
	April 2020	Released NI4OS-Europe newsletter, Issue no 1, also published on GRNET website and promoted via social media.
	July 2020	Released NI4OS-Europe newsletter, Issue no 2, also published on GRNET website and promoted via social media.
	November 2020	Released NI4OS-Europe newsletter, Issue no 3, also published on GRNET website and promoted via social media.

	February 2020	Press Release to the Greek Media and announcement on the NI4OS-Europe website : "Moving one step closer to the European Open Science Cloud: first resources have been on-boarded to NI4OS-Europe service catalogue".
	May 2020	Set up of the " NI4OS-EUROPE VS COVID-19 " page on NI4OS-Europe website.
	September 2020	NI4OS-Europe promoted during ESOF2020 session " Advancing R&I ecosystems in the Western Balkans with regard to their ERA integration ".
BG/IICT	25/09/2021	The achievements of NI4OS-Europe was presented at the 11-th National Information Day: "Open Science, Open Data, Open Access, Bulgarian OSC", which was organized as webinar form during the Int. conference "Digital Presentation and Preservation of Cultural and Scientific Heritage, 24-26 Sept 2020, Burgas, Bulgaria.
	26/11/2020	Promoting EOSC, FAIR principles and the NI4OS-Europe during the webinar " Open data, principles and management ".
HR/SRCE, RBI	26/11/2019	NI4OS-Europe project was promoted at the EOSC symposium 2019 held in Budapest as part of a presentation European Open Science Cloud: implementation and decision-making; coordination and adoption; harmony and awareness given by EOSC GB Croatian delegate Ivan Maric, during Open Plenary session.
	25/5/2020	SRCE participated in organization of e-IRG workshop about top challenges for the further development of e-Infrastructures in the European Research Area and beyond where NI4OS-Europe project was disseminated.
	8/7/2020	SRCE participated in the organization of EOSC Governance workshop with NI4OS-Europe partners where EOSC GB Croatian delegate Ivan Marić held presentation, EOSC Governance: where do we stand, where are we heading to.
	16/9/2020	During the PUBMET2020 conference, SRCE held presentation as part of NI4OS-Europe national capacity building training under the name National capacity Building NI4OS-Europe Training, Role of the national infrastructures.
	September 2019-ongoing	Sharing information about NI4OS-Europe project, EOSC and related documents, events on social media; CSI Facebook – 36; postEuraslic Facebook – 13 posts; CSI blog - 4 posts; CSI twitter – 10 posts.
	22/10/2019 – 04/12/2019	Sending information to e-mail lists with approx. 2000 researchers and librarians.
HU/ KIFU, DE	01/09/2020	Description about NI4OS-Europe project, promoting EOSC and FAIR principles on the KIFÜ microsite, is available via KIFÜ website.
	01/11/2020-ongoing	KIFÜ has designed and recorded video interviews with prominent researchers about data management, Open Science issues, EOSC possibilities in their area with the purpose of dissemination.
	ongoing	KIFÜ defined the framework of participation and the activities related to the Project Champion role and planned their roll-out in the user communities.
	March 18 2020– Nov 3 2020	HRDA meetup series : sharing information for researchers regarding EOSC, data management, FAIR and NI4OS-Europe project involvement. We organized 8 virtual meetups in this series.
	October 21 2021	For the request of The Association of Hungarian PhD and DLA Candidates we presented on the topic of Scientific Communication of the 21 st century,

		including EOSC, research infrastructures and the involvement of the NI4OS-Europe project.
	January 26 2021 – February 5 2021	Research data management meetup series : 10 virtual events were organized where we informed the participating researchers how to correctly fill the research data management plan made mandatory by the national research funder. In the presentation we introduced EOSC and NI4OS-Europe and FAIR as well.
	April 2019 - ongoing	Sharing information frequently on the instantscience.hu website regarding EOSC, FAIR data management and Open Science. Target audience is young researchers.
	September 2019-ongoing	Sharing information frequently on the national Open Science informational website on FAIR data, national events, NI4OS-Europe activities, and the development of EOSC.
	September 2019-ongoing	On the openscience.hu Facebook page we regularly share updates from the NI4OS-Europe Facebook page.
RO/ ICI BUCUREST I, UEFISCDI	10/03/2020	Overall presentation of the EOSC and NI4OS-Europe project were delivered during the “Open Science landscaping and strategic development in Romania”, organized by UEFISCDI in Bucharest.
SI/ARNES, UMUKM	September 2019-ongoing	Participation with NI4OS-Europe presentation in relevant national events.
	MO3, M10	Organisation of special sessions or workshops in conferences (e.g. organized by RDA).
RS/IPB, UOB	June 2020	IPB NI4OS-Europe team presented EOSC to researchers from the Astronomical Observatory Belgrade. Colleagues from the observatory were especially interested in the NI4OS-Europe capacity to support binary systems simulations using a large library of 1000 detailed evolutionary models.
	January-February 2021	Repository Policy Generator (RePol) was presented to the international repository managers associated with EIFL and the CORE Ambassadors community (as potential users).
	25/12/2019	NI4OS-Europe project was promoted at the Second Meeting of Open Science Pioneers in Serbia.
	06/11/2020	Promotional materials were sent to the participants of Open Science Days in Serbia and the NI4OS-Europe capacity building event in Serbia.
	06/11/2020	License Clearance Tool (LCT) and Repository Policy Generator (RePol) tool were presented during the NI4OS-Europe capacity building event in Serbia.
	March – December 2020	Survey results, datasets deposited in Zenodo (resulting from the NI4OS-Europe landscaping activity) and visualizations based on survey data were promoted during meetings with researchers and trainings for librarians.

Table 10: Marketing target: Researchers (communities, organizations, long tail of science)

Country/ partner	Implementing date	Description of action
All Partners	22/10/2019 – 04/12/2019	Survey – sending invitations to participate in the landscape survey of potential new thematic services/repositories providers.
	1/9/2019- 28/02/2021	Marketing NI4OS-Europe achievements during national capacity building training events.
	September 2019-ongoing	Sharing information about NI4OS-Europe generic and thematic services, EOSC and related documents on social media
	September 2019-ongoing	Sharing information on our social media platforms regularly regarding EOSC infrastructure and NI4OS-Europe repositories services
	September 2019-ongoing	Marketing during national dissemination events.
EL/ GRNET SA, ATHENA RC	16/10/2020	NI4OS-Europe promoted during ESOF2020 session “Advancing R&I ecosystems in the Western Balkans with regard to their ERA integration”
BG/IICT	24/07/2020, morning session	Participation with NI4OS-Europe presentation and take part in discussion during the online Workshop on Data Management organized by RDA BG Node. Promoting achievements and discussing involvement in preproduction testing of services.
	24/07/2020, afternoon	Online meeting with representatives from Bulgarian CLADA e-infrastructure consortium https://clada-bg.eu . During the meeting it was discussing possibility to cooperation between NI4OS-Europe project and CLADA e-infrastructure on a national level.
	29.01.2021	F2F meeting with representatives from Bulgarian DiSSCo–BG consortium (https://www.dissco.eu/bg/). During the meeting demonstration of NI4OS-Europe services/repositories was done and discussing possibility to collect biodiversity-associated service using the Bulgarian infrastructure involved in NI4OS-Europe project.
	15.01.2021	Zoom meetings with representatives from VMware Bulgaria regarding cooperation and using their services and tool for the needs of NI4OS-Europe project. Preparing agreement for 3 year cooperation including OSC.
HR/SRCE, RBI	27/2/2020	SRCE organized Croatian RDA event in city of Rijeka about research data management. During the event NI4OS-Europe brochure was handout to participants
HU/KIFU, DE	June 29 2021	Presentation on the HRDA meetup: 2-hour long presentation on what NI4OS-Europe’s role is in Open Science in South-East Europe
	September 2019-ongoing	KIFÜ team contacted potential academic service providers and offered support in defining their services for EOSC. Promoted its own participation with HPC as an example of service joining EOSC.
RO/ICI BUCURESTI, UEFISCDI	28.01.2021	For data and service providers the national training event (https://events.ni4os.eu/event/34/) provided detailed information about services and repositories on-boarding process, certification of data repositories, FAIR certification of research data.
SI/ARNES, UMUKM	September 2019-ongoing	Investigate the possibility to collect new thematic services/repositories.

	September 2019-ongoing	Participation with NI4OS-Europe presentation in relevant national events.
RS/ IPB, UOB	May 2020	IPB team demonstrated usage of the NI4OS-Europe repository service to other colleagues from the institute. The group from the Environmental physics laboratory expressed special interest in the usage of the repository for storing high-resolution, geo-referenced air pollution and meteorological data that cover Europe and the USA.
	January-February 2021	<u>Repository Policy Generator (RePol)</u> was presented to the international repository managers associated with EIFL and the CORE Ambassadors community.

Table 11: Marketing target: Data/service providers

Country/ partners	Implementing date	Description of action
All partners	22/10/2019 – 04/12/2019	Survey – sending invitations to participate in the landscape survey.
	September 2019-ongoing	Translated brochures on local languages about EOSC and FAIR were published on the local partners' webpages devoted to NI4OS-Europe project
	September 2019-ongoing	Sharing information about NI4OS-Europe project, EOSC and related documents, events on social media
	September 2019-ongoing	Sharing information on NI4OS-Europe activities on the project website
	September 2019-ongoing	Sharing information on our social media platforms regularly regarding EOSC, infrastructure and NI4OS-Europe
	September 2019-ongoing	Marketing during national dissemination events.
	September 2019-ongoing	Demonstrations of the NI4OS-Europe recommendations at meeting and events focused at funders and policy makers.
EL/ GRNET SA, ATHENA RC	Sept 2019 – June 2020	Participating in the consultations of the Greek Open Science Working Group which resulted in the formulation of the National Plan for Open Science .
BG/ IICT	10-11/12/2019	Promoting NI4OS-Europe project during the participation at the international conference "Research Infrastructures of the Future" (FUTURIS 2019), National Palace of Culture, Sofia, Bulgaria (distribution of project materials). Distribution of project materials. The event was focused on the synchronization of national and EU efforts towards the next programming period in the context of long-term sustainability of European research and innovation infrastructures. The event gathered high-level speakers and around 200 participants to the National Palace of Culture in Sofia, Link .
	9/12/2019	Promoting the NI4OS-Europe project during the visit of the Bulgarian president Rumen Radev in IICT, link .
	July 2020-December 2020	Participation in Open Science working group created by the Ministry of Education and Science (MES) in order to prepare the National Plan for Open Science (NPOS). As a result the NPOS was published by MES on 13.01.2021.

HR/ SRCE RBI	Feb 2020	SRCE had created webpage devoted to NI4OS-Europe project in Croatian language (webpage is available on the following link: https://www.srce.unizg.hr/NI4OS-Europe) which is constantly updated. Its purpose is to disseminate activities and events that promote NI4OS-Europe project within Croatian community.
HU/ KIFU, DE	June 29 2021	Presentation on the HRDA meetup: 2 hour long presentation on what NI4OS-Europe's role is in Open Science in South-East Europe
	May 20 2020	Presenting on the EOSC-Hub Week on the role of NI4OS-Europe in OS in South-East Europe
	April 2020	Social Media Campaign – Tackling Coronavirus Together: Sharing around 20 posts in a 10 day period on Twitter and Facebook on how NI4OS-Europe collaborates in the fight against COVID-19.
	September 2-4 2020	Networkshop 2020 : Presenting on current news of data management
	11-12/2020	Review and contribution EOSC bylaws, EOSC SRIA 0.9, KIFÜ participated in EOSC GB, EOSC GA
	September 2019-ongoing	KIFÜ promoted the NI4OS-Europe project and EOSC initiatives during the participation at the working group of National Research, Development and Innovation Office
	4 th quarter - ongoing	KIFU created a NI4OS-Europe subpage on their website and share updates on the project activities regularly
RO/ ICI BUCURESTI, UEFISCDI		A paper describing the NI4OS-Europe project and its related concepts is openly available on the website of the Romanian Journal of Information Technology and Automatic Control.
		Communities reach in a detailed article on the OS strategic development and the NI4OS-Europe involvement through a dedicated article in the Romanian Market Watch magazine, link .
RS/ IPB, UOB	September 2020	IPB's NI4OS-Europe team presented the NI4OS-Europe project to the Selectium company, which is Hewlett Packard enterprise representative in Serbia. This was organized as a part of series of meetings that led to the procurement of new equipment incorporated into the PARADOX-IV cluster.
	December 2019 – January 2020	NI4OS-Europe project was promoted during meetings with representatives of the Serbian Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development (preceding the establishment of the Team for Open Science in Serbia)
	16.01.2020	NI4OS-Europe project was promoted at the constitutional meeting of the Team for Open Science in Serbia

Table 12: Marketing target: Research funders, policy makers and general audience (incl. public and business organizations)